

Vertical flame spread with horizontal projection

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Preface

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Overview- In cases of façade fires or external venting fires in multi-storey buildings, a horizontal projection between the unprotected openings can serve as an effective measure to reduce upward flame spread. During conceptualization of this research, the primary goal was to explore the influence of horizontal projections on external fire spread. It was expected that the projection or barrier would prevent direct flame contact with the upper façade and restrict the vertical spread of the fire. However, this study mainly focused on understanding the impact of projections from a fire safety research perspective, without considering immediate practical implementation in buildings.

Abstract

This report consists of two main parts. The first part focuses on the results from several small-scale experiments. A vertical and combustible wall was exposed to external venting flames from a lower compartment. A non-combustible horizontal projection was used to reduce the direct impingement of the venting plume on the wall. The wall consisted of particle board and the horizontal projection was made of calcium silicate. The effectiveness of the horizontal projection in preventing vertical fire spread along the wall was studied for six different heat-release rates (33, 37, 42, 47, 51 and 56 kW).

The study investigated how different projection sizes impacted flame height, ignition, vertical temperature development, and char formation. In this study, 0.075 m and 0.1 m projections were used principally, while other projections (0.05 m and 0.2 m) were used for specific cases. The 0.1 m projection was more effective in reducing vertical flame heights and temperature development compared with the 0.075 m projection. The 0.1 m projection successfully prevented ignition on wall at 33 kW and 37 kW fires during the 10 min experimental duration, while the 0.075 m projection prevented ignition at 33 kW fire only. However, at higher heat-release rates, the wall ignited with both projections. Once ignition occurred, flame spread across the wall surface due to the combined effect of the burner and combustible gases from the pyrolysis process. The flame spread decreased after char formation on the wall. Char area and depth increased with higher heat-release rates for both projections, although there were no significant changes in vertical char height. A longer projection (0.2 m) was more effective by preventing ignition against 47 kW fire. The longer deflection distance restricted continuous attachment of flames and heat transfer to the wall.

The second part of this study involves a computational simulation study. A three-storey building model was constructed using the FDS software 'PyroSim', where the flame started at the bottom compartment. A 3.1 MW fire was simulated and spread to the upper floors through the window. Two types of projections of variable lengths (0, 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8 m) were placed over each floor. One projection type was an open-ended ceiling projection, while the other one was solid wall balustrade (such as balcony with railing). The exterior wall or façade of the building, along with the projection didn't include any combustible material. The simulation study allowed visualization and comparison of the flame trajectory and thermal behaviour of the ascending plume as it interacted with each projection type. Both projection types of several lengths (0.4 m, 0.6 m and 0.8 m) effectively reduced thermal impact, by 39% to 91%, on the upper floors compared with no projection, while the reduction increased with projection lengths. However, the temperature distribution at upper floor walls was affected by the projection types and lengths. Additionally, the thermal impact on a nearby building was also studied in these fire scenarios.

Sammendrag

Denne rapporten består av to hoveddeler. Den første delen fokuserte på resultatene fra en serie småskalaforsøk. En vertikal og brennbar vegg ble eksponert for flammer fra et lavereliggende forbrenningsrom. Et ikke-brennbart horisontalt framspring ble brukt for å redusere direkte flammekontakt på veggen. Veggen besto av sponplater, og det horisontale framspringet var laget av kalsiumsilikat. Effektiviteten av den horisontale projeksjonen i å forhindre vertikal brannspredning langs veggen ble undersøkt for seks ulike varmeutviklingsrater (33, 37, 42, 47, 51 og 56 kW).

Studien undersøkte hvordan ulike framspringensengde påvirket flammehøyde, antenning, vertikal temperaturutvikling og forkulling. I denne studien ble 0.075 m og 0.1 m framspring brukt som hovedalternativer, mens andre framspring (0.05 m og 0.2 m) ble brukt i spesifikke tilfeller. Framspringet på 0.1 m reduserte vertikale flammehøyder og temperaturutvikling sammenlignet med 0.075 m. Framspringet på 0.1 m forhindret antenning på veggen ved 33 kW og 37 kW brann under de 10 minuttene eksperimentene varte, mens framspringet på 0.075 m kun forhindret antenning ved 33 kW. Ved høyere varmeutviklingsrater tok veggen imidlertid fyr med begge framspring. Etter antenning intensiverte flammene på veggoverflaten seg som en kombinert effekt av brenneren og brennbare gasser fra pyrolyseprosessen. Flammene avtok etter forkulling på veggen. Forkullingsareal og -dybde økte med høyere varmeutviklingsrater for begge framspring, selv om det ikke var betydelige endringer i vertikal forkullingshøyde. Et lengre framspring (0.2 m) var mer effektivt ved å forhindre antenning ved 47 kW brann. Den lengre avbøyningsavstanden begrenset vedvarende flammekontakt og varmetransport til veggen.

Den andre delen av studien består av en numerisk simulering. En tre-etasjers bygningsmodell ble konstruert ved hjelp av FDS-programvaren PyroSim, hvor flammen startet i det nederste rommet. En brann på 3.1 MW ble simulert og spredte seg til de øvre etasjene gjennom vinduene. To typer horisontale framspring med variable lengder (0, 0.4, 0.6 og 0.8 m) ble plassert over hver etasje. En framspringtype var et åpent takframspring, mens den andre var en solid veggbalustrade (som en balkong med rekkverk). Den utvendige fasaden og framspringene inneholdt ikke brennbare materialer. Simuleringen tillot visualisering og sammenligning av flammebanen og den termiske oppførselen til den stigende flammesøylen i samspill med hver framspringtype. Begge framspringtypene med forskjellige lengder (0.4 m, 0.6 m og 0.8 m) reduserte effektivt den termiske belastningen med 39% til 91% på de øvre etasjene sammenlignet med intet framspring, og reduksjonen økte med framspringlengdene. Temperaturfordelingen på øvre etasjes vegger ble imidlertid påvirket av framspringtype og -lengde. I tillegg ble den termiske påvirkningen på en nærliggende bygning også studert for disse brannscenariene.

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Abbreviations

A_w	-	Area of the opening (m^2)
A_t	-	Total area of room boundaries less the window area (m^2)
A_{char}	-	Area of char (m^2)
b	-	Extinction coefficient (m^{-1})
C_p	-	Specific heat capacity of air (kJ/kg.K)
C_1	-	Constant (value 0.17 - Quintiere and Grove)
d	-	Depth of the compartment (m)
C_{depth}	-	Depth of char (mm)
g	-	Gravitational constant (ms^{-2})
h	-	Opening height (m)
h_l	-	Projection length (m)
h_w	-	Vertical distance from top of the opening (m)
H_f / z	-	Flame height above projection (m)
H_e	-	Projection height from compartment bottom (m)
H_n	-	Height of neutral plane (m)
H_{char}	-	Height of char (m)
I	-	Intermittency level of flame
$I_{rad.}$	-	Radiative heat flux (kW/m^2)
k	-	Empirical factor (value 0.013)
L	-	Mean flame height by Zukoski (m)
ℓ_1 & ℓ_2	-	Length dimensions of fire source (m)
\dot{m} / R	-	Burning rate (kg/s)
Q	-	Heat-release rate (kW)
\dot{Q}	-	Non-dimensional heat-release rate (kW)
$\dot{q}''_{conv.}$	-	Convective heat flux (kW/m^2)

R_f	-	Flame extension length beneath the projection (m)
R_o	-	Plume opening radius (m)
t_{ig}	-	Ignition time (s)
T_∞	-	Ambient temperature (K)
T_f / T	-	Flame plume temperature (K)
T_w	-	Wall temperature (K)
W	-	Compartment width (m)
X_p	-	Pyrolysis front (m)
α	-	Heat transfer coefficient ($\text{kW}/\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$)
ρ_∞	-	Density of ambient air (kgm^{-3})
ϵ_f	-	Emissivity of the flame
ϵ_w	-	Emissivity of the wall
σ	-	Stefan Boltzmann constant ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2 \text{K}^4$)
λ	-	Flame thickness (m)
ΔH	-	Heat of combustion (kJ/g)
Φ	-	Intersection ratio

Chapter 1

Introduction

Modern architecture shows a clear trend towards the construction of massive high-rise buildings. This characterizes the evolving nature of urban environments. This vertical shift has gone beyond the structure and influences the way people live, work, and interact with their surroundings. The CTBUH's (council on tall buildings and urban habitat) compiled data indicated a 441% increase in buildings with a height of 200 meters or more from 2000 to the end of 2016. There was an additional growth of 26.5% between 2016 and 2018 [1]. As a result, the field of fire protection is facing a major challenge period. Mammoser and Battaglia [2] have mentioned in their study that over 15,000 fires in tall buildings occurred in the United States between 1996 and 1998, where 75% of them were residential buildings. Most of the time, flames started at lower compartments. Rein and Bonner [3] listed 57 high-rise buildings where fire spread along the façade. The recent incident of the Grenfell Tower fire took the lives of more than 70 people and hundreds more were injured severely. The fire started at the fourth floor and spread along the façade of the building. Despite previous fires in high-rise building exterior cladding, the Grenfell disaster underscored the critical importance of robust fire prevention measures in building exteriors [4].

Many more events of façade fires have occurred with the growth in high-rise buildings overseas [1][5]. Fire spread along the exterior wall presenting a significant risk to both life safety and construction. In case of rescue operations, these fires are very challenging for the firefighters due to the limited height that can be reached using firefighting appliances. When a fire occurs in a lower compartment in a high-rise building, the remaining oxygen in the room fuels the fire growth and temperature starts to increase inside the room. Cracking of the window allows fresh oxygen to enter, and a sufficient supply of fuel may lead to flashover [6]. Yokoi [7] studied the development of room temperature enough to break the window with different fuel types. At 750°C, flashover occurred explosively ejecting 5 meters of flame to the outer wall. He also noted that 3 mm thick glass broke between 400°C and 500°C. The type of fuel and compartment size influenced these results. Radiation from the emerging flames pre-heats nearby combustible materials, intensifying pyrolysis and increasing the flaming region [8].

The risk of façade fires extends beyond the potential upward spread of flames. It also exerts a threat to the structural integrity of the building. Prolonged fire impingement to the external structural materials may increase their internal temperature radically. Thus, temperatures within the structural elements may reach critical values, resulting in structural collapse. Before fire spreads through the building, structural collapse poses an even greater danger to people

and the surroundings. **Figure 1** represents global incidents of high-rise fires resulting in casualties, highlighting the significant challenges in ensuring fire safety in these structures.

Figure 1. An overview of high-rise building fires around the world [63].

1.1 Existing knowledge on horizontal projection

In recent years, there has been a notable increase in research studies focused on understanding flames on external walls of buildings, particularly in the context of tall buildings with timber façades. Karyaparambil et al. [9] and Kamal [10] studied the effect of direct fire impingement on the outer combustible wall for both vertical and inclined façades. These experimental studies have delved into various aspects such as temperature profiles, flame heights, and the charring behaviour at outer combustible wall. While these investigations have significantly improved the understanding of the phenomena involved in façade fires, there has been relatively little research into effective preventative measures or solutions to mitigate the risk of such fires. Yokoi's [7] experimental approach revealed the effectiveness of using fireproof spandrels between the floors of a building and horizontal projection above the window against the vertical propagation of fire. Yokoi also found that the position and dimensions of a window have a substantial impact on the temperature distribution above. Horizontal projections are more effective at limiting flame spread when the window is short and narrow.

Oleszkiewicz [12] also investigated how projections, both horizontal and vertical, affect the spread of vertical fires. Oleszkiewicz placed both vertical and horizontal projections above a window opening. The heat flux on the wall above the window opening was reduced by 90% with horizontal projection, while a vertical projection resulted in a 50% increase in heat flux (Figure 2 b). These experiments demonstrate the effectiveness of horizontal projection to reduce the heat flux forwards on the surface above the window opening [2]. Gallea et al. [13] used a computational model (CFDS-FLOW 3D) to study the gas temperature distribution. The scenarios included three horizontal projections 0 m, 0.5 m, and 1 m for an eight-storey model building and a 1 MW heat source located on the third floor. The findings of this computational study comply with the observations of Yokoi [7] and Oleszkiewicz [14]. Horizontal projections can play a significant role in deflecting flames away from building façades by reducing the direct flame impingement [43]. The dimensions of the opening also impact the effectiveness of the projection over the compartment. Consequently, buildings with extensive openings may require additional fire protection measures to achieve a given level of safety.

Suzuki et al. [15] conducted an experimental ($\frac{1}{7}$ th scale) study on balcony effects against the upward moving flame in a multi-storey building. These authors used five balcony depths or projections (0 cm, 10 cm, 15 cm, 20 cm, and 25 cm). Experiments were conducted at four different heat-release rates (32 kW, 48 kW, 72 kW, and 95 kW). Fire room temperature increased with increasing balcony projection, but temperatures along the trajectory decreased gradually. In a further study, Suzuki et al. [16] found that the flame height decreased with increasing horizontal projection. Mammoser and Battaglia [2] later conducted a computational study on the use of balconies to observe temperature profiles. They utilized the experimental

study conducted by Suzuki et al. [15] as a reference for comparison. They also investigated several balcony geometries and their effects on upward fire spread. They found that non-combustible balustrades and open separation walls effectively reduced heat flux to the façade, delaying vertical fire spread. Figure 2 (a) illustrates a multi-storey building where fire spreads externally along the façade from the lower compartment to upper floors.

Figure 2. (a) A model multi-storey building with fire spreading from a lower compartment to upper floors through window openings, (b) Effect of horizontal and vertical projections on fire plume from the opening underneath by Oleszkiewicz (reproduced artwork) [11][12].

Hakkarainen and Oksanen [17] studied the fire behaviour of wooden façades in multi-storey houses, where they considered two fire scenarios, one intermediate sized and another large-scale post-flashover compartment fire. These experiments employed a variety of façade configurations. In one, a 400 mm deep cantilever used over the window of a spruce façade delayed the ignition time (approx. 3 min). They also predicted that a much deeper cantilever would prevent the ignition of the wooden façade.

1.2 Purpose of this experimental study

With an increasing number of fire-related incidents, the urgency to investigate the existing incidents and develop innovative solutions has never been more pressing. The aim of this study was to explore the effects of horizontal projections above the combustion compartment. A particle board imitating a combustible exterior wall in a tall building was subjected to continuous flame impingement from a lower fire-affected compartment. The dimensions of the compartment, opening size, and external wind conditions were deemed to be of minor importance in this study. Emphasis was given to exploring the effects of the projection on fire spread dynamics, ignition time, temperature variations, and charring behaviour of the combustible façade.

The experiments were conducted within a controlled fire laboratory environment, under a smoke-ventilated hood. Notably, sideward wind conditions were excluded from consideration during the experiments. It is pivotal to highlight that these experiments were not intended to replicate real-life fire scenarios. Instead, the purpose was to examine and study specific aspects under controlled conditions. In addition to small-scale experiments, the simulation study also played a crucial role in understanding vertical fire development with different horizontal projections in façade fires. The FDS study helped to bridge the gap left by the limitations of full-scale experiment in this thesis. FDS was used to explore and compare the vertical temperatures between buildings with and without projections. Thermal development on the upper floors of the fire-affected building and the upward flame trajectory were studied. Temperature development at the neighbouring building was also explored. Although FDS has limitations in accurately replicating real-life scenarios, the study provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of horizontal projections in reducing façade fire's impact.

1.3 Research questions

Several questions arose during the conceptualization of this study. This research aimed to find answers to these questions throughout the course of the investigation.

Experimental research questions:

1. How do different horizontal projection lengths influence the vertical temperature profiles during façade fires?
2. Do horizontal projections effectively reduce ignition times and flame heights on combustible façades across varying heat-release rates?

3. What is the influence of projection lengths on the distribution and intensity of charring along the combustible façade?

Simulation research questions:

1. How horizontal projections impact flame trajectories and vertical temperatures in façade fires, as simulated using Fire Dynamics Simulator?
2. How do variable geometry of projections differ in their ability to deflect flames and reduce upward flame spread along a building's façade?
3. How do different projections in fire-affected building influence the lateral flame spread and the temperature development at neighbouring building during such fire events?

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Flame propagation along vertical surface

The vertical spread of fire along a combustible façade involves a complex interplay of various factors. Combustible cladding materials may ignite due to continuous exposure to flames projecting from an opening or radiant heat source. In a multi-storey building, the fire can spread from a lower floor to upper floors. The intensity of the fire source and the characteristics of the external cladding determine the rate of spread. Flames venting from an opening impinge on the combustible cladding along the façade and thermally increase the temperature to cause pyrolysis—the breakdown of these materials into volatile gases, liquids, and char (further discussed on section 2.2). Not every exterior cladding made of combustible materials can sustain vertical propagation of flames. Materials like cellulosic fibre cement sheets, which are combustible, do not play a significant role in fire spreading. In the case of composite materials, the potential to sustain vertical propagation is affected by both the outer protective layer applied to the core material and the ability to maintain structural integrity when exposed to flames [6][18]. For instance, Aluminium composite panels (ACPs) with polyethylene cores are highly prone to vertical flame spread because the polyethylene core is flammable. Under fire, the thin aluminium layers can peel away quickly, exposing the core and intensifying the fire spread [19].

According to Hashemi [20], flame spread on a surface involves a moving flame near the part of the surface undergoing pyrolysis. This process differs from the propagation of flames in a premixed fuel and oxygen system, as the flame spreads across the surface due to the surface being heated by the flame. Saito and Quintiere [21] stated that the flame propagates when the unignited part of the fuel undergoes heating, reaching a temperature with intense pyrolysis. This heating occurs through convective and radiative heat transfer from the flames that envelop the fuel surface. Brehob et al. [8] described a physical model of the mechanism of upward flame spread and ignition process along a vertical surface (Figure 3 c). Where a vertical wall is subjected to a one-dimensional external fire source, as the flame front advances upward, it heats the unburned material ahead of the pyrolysis front through heat flux from both the flames and external radiation. This is very similar to the model (Figure 3 b) discussed by Hashemi [20].

Upward movement of a flame is also influenced by the façade geometry. Flame directions and propagation also change with the angle of the façade inclination, side confinements and other conditions. Kamal [10] found that the façade orientation has dominant impact on flame spread,

Figure 3. (a) Change in the mode of surface flame spread with the slope angle, (b) Upward flame spread along a vertical wall, and (c) Heat flux distribution along a vertical wall from one dimensional exposed fire source. Figures are regenerated based on refs. [8][20].

ignition time, and charring behaviour. He observed that char properties and ignition time increase linearly with positively tilted façade. Flame behaviour at various surface angles is illustrated in Figure 1 (c). Hashemi [20] stated that with increase in the angle of inclination, the flame begins to crawl over the surface as the angle between the surface and the flame flow is reduced, enhancing heat transfer and accelerating flame spread.

While the orientation and inclination of façades significantly influence the behaviour of flame spread, additional geometrical features such as projections or balconies can also alter the flame's natural upward trajectory and spread pattern. A horizontal projection or any barrier above the combustion compartment redirects the flame's original trajectory. However, flame's total length along its axis remains unchanged and the flame may redirect towards its original trajectory after deflection [23][62]. Figure 4 illustrates an external venting flame scenario with a horizontal projection above. The flames follow a deflected path (b) and then return to their original path (c). Where, h is the opening height and H_f is the flame height above the projection.

Figure 4. Assumed trajectories of flames emerging from a compartment opening and with a horizontal projection on top. The figure is based on refs. [23][62].

2.1.1 Vertical flame heights

Flame height is a key parameter of flame spread. Under free-burning conditions, flame height refers to the vertical distance from the flame's base to the visible top edge. Flame height is influenced by several factors such as the type of fuel, combustion rate and oxygen concentrations. In cases with vertical façades, flame height can be defined similarly, but additional factors also affect the flame height. The proximity of the façade can cause the flames to extend higher than in a free burn condition. The material of the façade, the geometry, and the heat transfer properties significantly influence the flame height. Closer flame attachment with the façade causes heat transfer to adjacent materials, increasing the likelihood of ignition and flame propagation.

The lower luminous part of the flaming region remains relatively steady, while the upper section exhibits intermittent behaviour. Occasionally, vortex structures, varying in intensity, can be seen forming near the flame's base and moving upwards [24]. McCaffery [25] divided the fire plume into three regions, the continuous, intermittent and plume regions. He described continuous flame height where flame exists 100% of the time, in intermittent region where it varies from 10% to 90% and above is buoyant plume region. A 50% intermittency definition is widely used for flame height analysis [26][27]. According to Zukoski, the mean flame height (L) is defined as the vertical distance from the fire source where the flame's intermittency decays to 0.5. Figure 5 shows schematically the variation in flame intermittency with the mean flame height indicated. The intermittency starts at its highest value at initial part of the flame, becomes lower in the outer flame region, and eventually reaches zero [28].

Figure 5. (a) Mean flame height from measurements of intermittency as shown by Zukoski et al. [28], (b) Flame height (H_f) as measured vertically from the combustion chamber.

Flame heights are commonly assessed through visual observation of the luminous flames. The predominant technique involves visually identifying the height of the blue reaction zone (intermittency 0.4 - 0.6). This zone is significant because stoichiometric conditions exist on the oxygen side, resulting from CO_2 and CH^* chemiluminescence [29]. For greater accuracy, thermal or infrared camera-based methods can be employed. Newman and Wieczorek [30] determined chemical flame heights to distinguish them from luminous flame heights based on visual observation. Ligang et al. [31] used video recording and software processing of footage to measure flame height. A similar approach, using image processing and binarization, has also been applied in this experimental study to determine vertical flame heights.

2.1.2 Plume geometry with a horizontal projection

Previous studies [23][32-35] have investigated compartment fires experimentally and through numerical simulation, focusing on the analysis of plume geometry and correlations for fire plumes venting from an opening. These studies considered external fire spread and validated engineering calculations for real fires using simulation or scaled experimental models. The primary focus has been on flame heights, compartment size, plume geometry and flame spreading. Figure 6 illustrates the impact of projection implementation on plume trajectory and vertical spreading behaviour. The continuous plume region shortened vertically while the lateral flame distance increased.

Delichatsios et al. [32] proposed that the ejected plume from a compartment opening can be considered as a fire plume produced from a rectangular fire source. Figure 7 represents assumed rectangular fire source beneath the horizontal projection, where ℓ_1 and ℓ_2 are the dimensions of the fire source respectively.

Correlations based on the study by Delichatsios et al. –

$$\frac{H_f}{\ell_1} = 3.2 (\dot{Q}_l^*)^{2/3} \text{ for } \dot{Q}_l^* < 1, \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

$$\frac{H_f}{\ell_2} = 3.2 (\dot{Q}_l^*)^{2/5} \text{ for } \dot{Q}_l^* > 1, \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

$$\dot{Q}_l^* = \frac{\dot{Q}}{\rho_\infty \times C_p \times T_\infty \times \sqrt{g} \times (\ell_1)^{5/2}} \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

Here, ρ_∞ is the density of the ambient air [kgm^{-3}], C_p is the specific heat capacity of air [kJ/kg.K], T_∞ is the ambient temperature [K], and g is the gravitational constant [ms^{-2}].

Figure 6. Plume geometry without (left) and with (right) horizontal projection.

Lu et al. [36] studied sideward plume extension after the flame had emerged from an opening beneath horizontal projections in vertical fire spreading scenarios. They assumed the rectangular fire source by Delichatsios et al. produce almost symmetrical thermal plumes and considered an equivalent half circle fire source with radius, R_o (Figure 7). Mckeen and Liao [37] examined the impact of horizontal projections on lateral flame spread from a lower compartment. Both studies focused on modelling the plume geometry from the opening beneath the horizontal projection.

These studies were influenced by the systematic research of Delichatsios et al. [32] on flame heights in façades from fires in enclosures of varying geometry.

Figure 7. Plume geometry resulting from the compartment opening beneath a horizontal projection. Figures are regenerated based on ref. studies [36][37].

The following equations from recently mentioned studies [32-37] can be used to calculate flame extension length (sideward plume length) R_f , beneath the projection,

$$R_f = 0.0283 \left(\frac{\phi \dot{Q}}{\sqrt{H_e - H_n}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (\text{eq. 4})$$

$$\phi = \frac{R_o^2 (H_f - H_e) + R_o C_1 ((H_f - H_n)^2 - (H_e - H_n)^2) + \frac{1}{3} C_1^2 ((H_f - H_n)^3 - (H_e - H_n)^3)}{R_o^2 (H_f - H_n) + R_o C_1 (H_f - H_n)^2 + \frac{1}{3} C_1^2 (H_f - H_n)^3} \quad (\text{eq. 5})$$

$$\ell_1 = (A_w \sqrt{h})^{2/5} \quad (\text{eq. 6})$$

$$\ell_2 = (A_w h^2)^{1/4} \quad (\text{eq. 7})$$

$$R_o = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi} \ell_1 \ell_2} \quad (\text{eq. 8})$$

The intersection ratio ϕ is a function of plume opening radius R_o , which is the difference between the height of the horizontal projection and flame. From equation 5, the value of ϕ can be calculated using the average flame height along the façade (H_f), the projection height from the bottom of compartment (H_e), the compartment opening height (h), the height of neutral plane (H_n), and a constant C_1 (value 0.17, from the study by Quintiere and Grove [35]). The lengths scales ℓ_1 and ℓ_2 can be calculated based on the flow geometry of flames exiting through the enclosure opening [32].

2.2 Wood decomposition, ignition and charring

Decomposition of wood under heat exposure follows several stages. Initially, dehydration occurs followed by pyrolysis, ignition, and charring. The initial stage involves moisture evaporation from the wood structure, which typically occurs at temperatures around 100 °C. As the temperature increases, bound water in the wood's cellular structure is released. As the temperature rises beyond 200 °C, pyrolysis processes start. Pyrolysis refers to the breakdown of wood's organic compounds due to heat in an oxygen-deprived environment and resulting in simpler chemical components. During this stage, volatile gases such as carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, methane, and various organic compounds are released, alongside solid residues like char. The pyrolysis process is highly dependent on the rate of heating or heat transfer to the material and the temperature development. Low-temperature pyrolysis primarily produces char and tar, while high-temperature pyrolysis results in more gaseous products.

Figure 8. Charred wood in cross-section with charred region, pyrolysis region, and unburnt region.

The produced combustible gases due to pyrolysis process mix with oxygen and ignition occurs. This typically happens at temperatures between 300 °C and 400 °C. The ignition of these gases produces visible flames and generates heat, which can further accelerate the pyrolysis of the remaining wood. As the combustion process continues, the surface of the wood begins to char (Figure 8). Charring is the formation of a carbon-rich residue resulting from the thermal degradation of wood. This char layer acts as an insulative barrier, slowing down the heat transfer to the unpyrolyzed wood beneath and thus protecting the inner layers from rapid degradation. The physical layer of char prevents oxygen to reach inside the underlying wood. Since oxygen is essential for combustion, its restricted access further reduces the pyrolysis and combustion rates of the uncharred wood [38 - 41].

Suzanne et al. [42] studied how various factors, such as external heat flux, controlled atmospheres, material responses, and gas velocities, influence the decomposition, ignition, and charring behaviour of wood under fire conditions. The findings highlight that cumulative exposure effectively predicts char depth and that can be a valuable insight for fire investigation and understanding fire dynamics across different scenarios. They found that even though self-extinguishment may occur, there was still virgin wood beneath the char period. Thus, char depth is an important quantity to assess. Char depth is directly related to the combustion process, heat exposure and duration. The higher the heat intensity, the faster the charring, and the deeper the resulting char.

2.3 Approaches to heat flux estimation

The flame emerging from the compartment is the primary source of energy and for heat transfer to the vertical wall above. This energy is transmitted to the wall through both radiation and convection. As the flame rises, it emits radiation, directly affecting the wall surface. Simultaneously, the hot gases produced by the flame induce convective heat transfer to the wall surface. The total heat flux determines if ignition on the wall surface will occur.

Law [22] developed a model that estimated both radiant and convective heat transfer to the external columns and beams of a building, based on given compartment and opening dimensions. Flame thickness was assumed constant along the height. Oleszkiewicz [11] modified the model for calculating heat transfer to the building façade. He mentioned that the assumptions in Law's model resulted in an unrealistic abrupt change in the calculated heat transfer in the area near the top of the flame. So, he assumed the shape of the flame to be triangular when impinged on the exterior façade (as shown in Figure 9) and modified the expressions accordingly.

2.3.1 Heat flux through convection

The convective heat flux density can be expressed as [11],

$$\dot{q}''_{conv.} = \alpha \times (T_f - T_w)$$

where,

α - convective heat transfer coefficient

T_f - fire plume temperature

T_w - wall temperature

Law's equation to estimate the convective heat transfer coefficient (α) assumed a free burning fire, giving higher heat flux density to the exposing wall [18][22].

$$\alpha = 0.0132 \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{A_w} \right)^{0.6} \times \left(\frac{1}{d} \right)^{0.4}$$

where,

\dot{m} = rate of burning

A_w = area of the opening

d = depth of the compartment

Oleszkiewicz [11] derived the heat transfer coefficient expression as,

$$\alpha = k \left(\frac{R}{A_w} \right)^{0.6}$$

where,

R - rate of burning

A_w - area of opening

k - empirical factor

Oleszkiewicz assumed that the mass velocity within the window plume is proportional to the ratio of burning rate to the window area. The empirical factor value, k was determined by correlating the calculated convective heat flux density with the experimental measurements, which gave $k = 0.013$ [11][18], and :

$$\alpha = 0.013 \left(\frac{R}{A_w} \right)^{0.6}$$

Oleszkiewicz mentioned Thomas's [44] equation for burning rate (R) in his study,

$$R = 0.18 (1 - \exp(-0.036 \times A_t / (A_w h^{1/2}))) / (d/W)^{1/2}$$

where,

A_t - total area of room boundaries less the window area

h - height of the opening

d - room depth

W - room width

Buchanan [45] also provided equation to calculate approximate value of burning rate (kg/s) in his book. He suggested a design procedure to calculate the size and shape of the expected flame from a window and then calculate radiation back to the building via the window above. Burning rate based on heat-release rate as,

$$R = 0.0015 \frac{Q}{\Delta H_a}$$

where, Q is the average heat-release rate in kW, ΔH_a is the calorific value (heat of combustion) of propane in kJ/g, and the factor 0.0015 is an estimated value.

Figure 9. Assumed triangular shape of flame impingement on the wall as given by Oleszkiewicz [11].

2.3.2 Heat flux through radiation

Based on the flame geometry and temperature, Law [22] considered radiative heat flux density as,

$$I_{rad.} = \epsilon_f \times \epsilon_w \times \sigma \times T^4$$

where,

ϵ_f - emissivity of the flame

ϵ_w - emissivity of the wall [46]

σ – Stefan Boltzmann constant

T - absolute temperature of flame along the wall

Law [22] also derived equations to calculate temperatures for both natural and forced draft conditions, assuming that the temperature remains constant along the width of the window and across the plume depth. For the current study, thermocouples at various heights along the wall provided gas temperature data during the experiments. Average temperature data have been

utilized to compute heat flux densities at different heights along the wall. This approach appeared reasonable, but calculated temperatures using Law's method gave higher values than the measured temperatures, as noted by Turan and Klopovic [47]. They also indicated in their study that the flame temperature varies linearly with distance along the flame axis.

Local emissivity of the flame was calculated using the recommended equation by Law [22], which was also mentioned by Oleszkiewicz [11],

$$\epsilon_f = 1 - \exp(-b \times \lambda)$$

where,

b – extinction coefficient (0.09 ft^{-1} in U.S. Unit or 0.3 m^{-1} in S.I. Units)

λ – flame thickness

A constant flame thickness was assumed in the Law's original radiant heat transfer model, which was modified by Oleszkiewicz later. He assumed a triangular flame shape along the wall height and flame thickness near the top of the window was set to be two-thirds the height of the opening (as shown in Figure 9).

A variable flame thickness along the vertical direction can be expressed as,

$$\lambda = \frac{2}{3} h \left(\frac{z - h_w}{z} \right)$$

where,

z – height of the flame above the opening

h_w - vertical distance from the top of opening

In current study, the extra travel length of the flame or projection length (h_l) has considered in the calculation process. So, one arrives at the following expression,

$$\lambda = \frac{2}{3} h \left(\frac{z - h_w}{z} \right) + h_l$$

Chapter 3

Experimental Set-up

Several small-scale experiments were planned for this study to observe fire spreading along a vertical combustible façade with horizontal projection over the combustion compartment. The total number of experiments was not fixed but was estimated to some extent. The experimental structure had to be sustainable, firm, and mobile. The combustion compartment was constructed to resemble an actual compartment in a tall building where flames break through the window opening and contacts the exterior wall of the building. Particle boards were used as combustible façade above the combustion compartment. The ceiling of the compartment was extended horizontally at different lengths to form projections. A graphic representation of the experimental set-up has been demonstrated in [Figure 10](#).

The horizontal projection above the combustion compartment was intended to act as a barrier or deflector against the rising plume venting through the window. The projection was expected

Figure 10. Experimental layout. (a) Front view (secondary camera position) of the setup where the thermocouple tips are shown as black points, (b) Side view (main camera position) of the experimental setup, where the horizontal projection length over the compartment was variable and the combustible particle board was supported by a wooden frame.

to reduce the impact and limit flame spread along the wall. However, the effectiveness of the projection, and to what extent it could mitigate fire spread was uncertain. The side-view camera played a crucial role in observing the impact of the projection on the venting flames from the compartment and analysing the flame's trajectory along the wall. The front-view position helped to observe the flame spread along the vertical wall, transitions of the flame, and flame heights.

3.1 Components

3.1.1 *Fire compartment*- It was made with lightweight concrete and placed on a wooden pallet for mobility. Light weight concrete was used as it has a higher insulation value than regular concrete and is easy to handle.

Dimensions (inner) - length 0.4 m × width 0.2 m × height 0.4 m

Opening - width 0.2 m × height 0.4 m

The ceiling of the compartment was extended manually and the gaps between the plates were filled with fibrous strips before every experiment. The compartment could sustain high temperatures during the experiments, where flames appeared to fill the full volume and emerge from the ventilation opening. A burner 0.1 m × 0.1 m was placed at the lower middle end of the compartment (as shown in [Figure 7 b](#)). The burner was connected to the propane tank and flow meter through a pvc hose.

3.1.2 *Combustible board*- Here particle boards were used to imitate the external wall over a combustion compartment. These boards are made of wood particles and saw-dust, combined with binders or adhesives to form a sheet-like panel having a lower degree of deformation against fire. These boards have also lower moisture content ($\geq 5\%$) [[58](#)]. More detailed properties are outlined in [Table 2](#).

Dimensions- length 1.2 (± 0.02) m × width 0.6 (± 0.02) m × thickness 0.012 m

3.1.3 *Horizontal projection*- The horizontal projection used in this study was made of calcium silicate. The silicate plate was adjusted and modified up to the desired length over the compartment. Calcium silicate was chosen due to its low density and good thermal insulation properties. It was very easy to install, and the thickness of the plate was 0.05 m.

3.1.4 Thermocouple- A total of 18 K-type thermocouples were used along the board during the experiments at every 0.1 m interval (as shown in [Figure 10](#)). 9 thermocouples were placed 0.01 m above the board surface (flame exposed side of the board). Furthermore, 9 thermocouples were inserted 0.006 m (± 0.001 m) inside from the rear side of the board. These thermocouples are able to measure over a wide range of temperatures (-270 to 1260 °C) with fast response.

3.1.5 Gas flow- Propane gas was used as fuel. Propane has high energy density and can generate intense and controlled flames. Also, it has a distinctive odour that helps to detect the leakage. Different gas flow rates were used and controlled by a flow meter to adjust the flow. The mass flow rate of propane (\dot{m}_f) multiplied by the heat of combustion (ΔH) was assumed to be the total heat-release rate, assuming 100% combustion efficiency. The heat of combustion of propane is -2044 kJ/mol or $-(2044/44) = -46.45$ kJ/g, where 44 g/mol is the molar weight of C_3H_8 [59].

3.1.6 Support frame- Wooden frames were made to mount the particle board and thermocouples. Particle boards were fastened with screws using two side arms of the

Figure 11. Support frames for holding the particle board and thermocouples (9 thermocouples drilled through the board up to 0.01 m above the board surface and other 9 drilled 0.006 m inside from rear side of the board).

frame in vertical positions. A dead weight was also embedded in the frame for more stability. Thermocouples were also supported by a wooden frame abaft the particle board (as shown in Figure 10). A wooden scale was attached to the side frame to align the camera height properly (as shown in Figure 11).

Table 1. Dimensions and experimental factors.

Opening dimension of the combustion chamber, $w \times h$ (m)	Area of the opening, A_w (m^2)	Ventilation factor, $A_w\sqrt{h}$ ($m^{2.5}$)	Gas flow rate, \dot{m}_f (g/s)	Heat of combustion, ΔH (kJ/g)	Heat-release rate, Q (kW)
0.2 × 0.4	0.08	0.0506	0.7	46.45	33
			0.8		37
			0.9		42
			1		47
			1.1		51
			1.2		56

Table 2. Specifications and parameters of the materials used in experiments.

Properties	Combustible board	Inert plate (compartment ceiling)	Lt. Concrete (compartment walls)
Composition	80.46% wood, 12.19% adhesive, 0.91% wax, 0.06% ammonia solution, 0.53% ammonium nitrate, 0.35% urea, and 5.51% water [58]	Calcium silicate [9]	Sand, lime and water [9]
Thickness (cm)	1.2	5	20
Density (kg/m^3)	630- 700 (approx.)	225	290 (approx.)
Thermal heat conductivity (W/m.K)	0.13	0.074	0.076
Specific heat capacity (J/kg.K)	1420-1450	840	1050

3.2 Camera positioning

Two cameras were used during each experimental session (as shown in [Figure 12 a](#)). The secondary or front view camera was strategically placed closer to the combustion compartment to capture the critical aspect of flame height variations throughout the combustion event. The distance was 1.5 m from the compartment throughout all the experiments. A Panasonic cam W580 was used as the secondary camera. The specifications and details are documented in [Table 3](#). The main purpose was to obtain the flame heights along the board. This camera also revealed valuable insights into the energy release and intensity of the burning process. Its proximity to the compartment allowed for detailed observation of the flame front and its movement.

A Sony NX80 camera was used as the main camera. It was placed 2.65 m away from the compartment and positioned sidewise. The purpose of the sidewise positioning was to enable observation of the flame effects and behaviour around the projection over the combustion compartment. The quality of the footage and resolution were better than the front one. The sensor and lens were also better and bigger. This camera offered a lateral view of the entire setup, ensuring a comprehensive visual understanding of the flame dynamics.

Stable mounts and tripods securely held the cameras in place, avoiding any unnecessary movements or vibrations that could compromise the quality of the footage. These measures provided consistent and clear images that improved visualization and subsequent analyses. A timer was placed such that it was recorded by both cameras. Thus, the two recordings could easily be aligned. It helped to observe the parameters from both angles at the same time. [Figure 12](#) gives a top view of experimental set up and camera positions.

Table 3. Camera specifications.

Main Camera (side view) – Sony NXCAM80 [60]	Secondary Camera (front view) – Panasonic HC-W580 [61]
Sensor - 1"-Type CMOS Sensor	Sensor - 1/5-inch MOS Sensor
Resolution- 14.3 Megapixel	Resolution - 2.51 megapixels
ISO – 400 (Auto)	ISO – Auto
Frame rate – 25/sec	Focal length – (2.06 – 103 mm)
Focal length – (9.3 - 111.6mm)	Frame rate – 25/sec
Frame size – 1080 × 1920 (height × width)	Frame size – 720 × 1280 (height × width)

(a)

Side view
(main camera
position)

Front view
(secondary camera
position)

(b)

Figure 12. (a) Top view of experimental layout and camera positioning, (b) Example of images from each of the cameras.

Chapter 4

Data Analysis Techniques

Experimental investigation of flame propagation along a combustible wall with a horizontal projection involved various quantities. The flame height served as a basic indicator of the propagation process. The temperature data reflected vertical thermal behaviour along the combustible board. Charring characteristics were investigated to quantify the depth, volume, density and extent of the charred layer of the wall. The ignition time was another important quantity, defined as the time it took for the wall to ignite.

Data collection and processing were carried out using computer software. Statistical tools and algorithms were used to process the large amounts of data efficiently. The computer software also facilitated visualization of the data and enabled creation of graphical representations. Visual observations also provided valuable context for identifying qualitative aspects of fire behaviours, such as flame patterns, propagation, and the general progression of the combustion process. Data analysis techniques that combined computer software processing and visual observations have been used in this study.

4.1 Measurement of flame heights (H_f)

Flame height is an essential quantity for determining how far the flame may propagate along the combustible façade. Furthermore, it is connected to the heat transfer associated with the flame spread. Flames emit heat, and their height affects the distance that radiant heat can travel. During every experiment, two cameras were used to capture the video footage (as shown in [Figure 12](#)). Footage from the secondary camera (front view) was used to determine the flame heights along the wall. A scale was fixed on the side of the wooden frame to adjust the camera focusing position. The upper visible detached flaming areas, separated from the main flame or the flamelets, were also considered here (as shown in [Figure 13 a](#)). Since flamelets transfer heat flux to the surface of the board and set stability limits to the flow. Flames or flamelets crossed out of the frame boundary, were considered to have reached the maximum flame heights (1.2 m).

Single frames or images were extracted from the video footage (for individual experiments). The extracted RGB images from the videos were converted into grayscale images and then finally to threshold or binary images. This process is called image thresholding or binarization. Each image length was preset to 1.2 m (same as the wall height above the compartment) and a

(a)

(b)

Figure 13. (a) Flame height measurement as explained in the main text, (b) Thresholding or binarization steps of extracted image for flame height measurement (RGB to threshold image).

reference black image grid was created for the individual experiment video. Other binarized images of the same video clip were compared with the reference image through quasi-2D interpolation method to measure the top vertical pixel position. [Figure 13 b](#) represents the steps from RGB to binary image for measuring flame height. The uppermost visible luminous point (pixel position) in the image was considered the peak length or top flame height. In image processing it is important to separate noise from the image background. To minimize errors, different threshold values or binarization factors were used, from 0.4 to 0.7. The values were considered after visual verification of whether the binary image was most similar to the grayscale or RGB image. Even though operations took longer but served a satisfactory result. Size and exposure were set the same for all images. In addition, the camera position, exposure, ISO values, and lab room environment were optimized according to the process.

4.2 Measurement of charring properties

4.2.1 Char height (H_{char})

Char heights (H_{char}) were measured using a meter tape from the bottom of the board ([Figure 14 a](#)). The uppermost visible blister or crack spot on the board surface defined the height. After every experiment, each board was marked with heat-release rate, projection length and experiment number. With a high-definition camera, pictures were taken specifically for further processing after experiments.

4.2.2 Char area (A_{char})

Char area (A_{char}) was measured in two ways,

1. Initially, the visibly cracked area on the board surface was identified and later quantified using computer software. An image of the specific board was processed, and the charred region was delineated to determine the area (m^2). This image processing phase involved adjusting cropping ratios and thresholding techniques. A contour or colour mapping algorithm was also utilized to determine the charred region visually on the board. [Figure 14 \(b\)](#) illustrates the Char area and the regions of pre-pyrolysis or soot.
2. After cutting the board panels width wise (see [Figure 15 a](#)), areas were considered based on the minimum measurable char depth (≥ 0.4 mm) from the cross section (see [Figure 14 c](#)).

Figure 14. (a) Char height identification after experiment (visual), (b) Char area identification after colour mapping of the board image (visual blister or crack formation on board + contour plots), (c) Measured char depth (≥ 0.4 mm) values from the cut panel (see Figure 15) give the char height and area over the board surface.

4.2.3 Char depth (d_{char})

The decision making process regarding char depth measurement was a critical aspect of the methodology. Initially, manually removing char from board panels and measuring the depth using a vernier scale was considered. However, upon careful evaluation, several factors weighed against this approach. Despite implementing proper safety precautions, including protective gears, the risk of penetrating char particles remained a concern. Besides, it would have been a laborious and time-consuming task.

An alternative approach then came up, which involved cutting the charred board width wise at every 50 mm (0.05 m) interval and measuring the depth from the cross-section of the cut panels. Each cut piece was labelled according to the experiment number, heat-release rate, and projection size. The depths of char along the cut panels were assumed to be uniform along 50 mm height. Then, the labelled pieces were photographed separately for further processing. A

computer program was utilized to analyse the images and measure char depth accurately. Figure 15 (a) illustrates the cutting process of charred board panels. A grid system was introduced consisting of 24 grid lines at every 25 mm distance positioned along the width of the cut piece.

Figure 15. (a) Illustration of the charred board cutting process, (b) Determination of char depths from the cross-section of a cut panel. The cut panels were labelled, and grid lines were placed at 25 mm (2.5 cm) intervals to measure the char depth of the specific cell. Char depths were measured from the rear side of the particle board to upwards.

This grid system spanned the entire width of the piece (60 cm). The thickness of the board panel (1.2 cm) was preset into the program. Subsequently, char depth was measured from each grid cells in the image of the cut piece. The measured depth (≥ 0.4 mm) was considered as input data, with each cell representing depths at every 25 mm (2.5 cm) distance. The process is shown in Figure 15 (b).

4.3 Determination of ignition time (t_{ig})

Ignition on the board surface was determined visually using images extracted from the side-view camera footage (3 frames/sec). A stopwatch was strategically positioned beside the compartment in such a way that it remained visible in the camera's field of view. This setup allowed for precise tracking of time throughout the experiment. The starting time was taken as the moment when flame was vented from the compartment opening.

Figure 16. Ignition on the board surface, with timer/stopwatch for recording of time.

Chapter 5

Results

This chapter presents observations and outcomes from the experiments, focusing on flame heights, ignition on particle board, temperature distribution at the surface and within the particle board, and charring characteristics under varying heat-release rates.

Further analysis at the observed phenomena will be given in the discussion chapter. Four horizontal projections (0.05 m, 0.075 m, 0.1 m and 0.2 m) were employed over the compartment, with gas flows ranging from 0.7 g/s to 1.2 g/s (heat-release rates 33 kW to 56 kW). Experimental duration was 10 min (600 seconds). For the 0.01 m projection, three experiments were conducted for all heat-release rates. For the 0.075 m projection, two experiments were performed for each case. Specifically, for the 0.05 m and 0.2 m projections, gas flow of 0.7 g/s and 1 g/s were used only. Six experiments failed due to gas flow malfunctions or faulty thermocouples, resulting in the absence of recorded data for these instances.

5.1 Impact of a horizontal projection

When flames emerged from the compartment opening, the protruding projection deflected the flame front horizontally. The flame rose vertically due to a continual fuel supply and created a swirling impact on the board surface. The rising flames encountered the board surface at an optimal angle and spread vertically with increasing gas flow. A gap or hollow space formed beneath the contact zone ([Figure 17 a](#)), as for the Coandă effect. Henri Coandă discovered this effect in 1910, demonstrating that fluid jets bend to follow curved surfaces as they pass over them while pulling in air along the way. Sharp angles and deflecting surfaces can turn flows by up to 180 degrees. Adding a small surface "lip" where the jet begins increased initial deflection due to a low-pressure vortex forming behind the lip, pulling the jet towards the surface [[48](#)][[49](#)].

Without the projection, flames typically spread from the bottom and moved upward along the wall (see [Figure 6](#)). Heat transfer to the wall significantly facilitate flame propagation along the façade [[9 - 11](#)]. Char formation on the wooden façade limits the heat transfer to the wall and slows the pyrolysis process. Char acts as an insulation layer against flame. However, the introduction of horizontal projection over the compartment opening increased the flame turbulence. Projection likely disrupted the smooth flow of gases, causing eddies and vortices. The increased turbulence enhanced the mixing of hot gases and air, intensifying combustion.

This also created a gap between the opening and the wall, forming a low pressure vortex (as shown in Figure 17 b).

Figure 17. (a) Flame impingement on board surface (reference flow – 0.9 g/s (42 kW HRR) with 0.1 m horizontal projection). Coherent flame attachment and ignition can be noticed a few cm above the board, (b) Illustration of the Coandă effect, low pressured air vortices formed beneath the contact zone of jet fluid and surface [48].

The current study extensively analysed the impact of 0.075 and 0.1 m horizontal projections at various heat-release rates. Additionally, the behaviour of a longer projection (0.2 m) was observed at 47 kW fire over 10 min flame exposure period. With increased heat-release rates, the energy released from the combustion process increased, resulting in more heat and combustion gases being generated. This caused stronger buoyant forces and led to a rise in flame heights as a larger volume of hot gases ascended more rapidly. The vertical temperature distribution was influenced by heat-release rates and horizontal projections. As heat-release rates increased, the temperatures along the plume height increased as well. The horizontal projections altered the shape and trajectory of upward gas flame.

0.075 m projection

0.1 m projection

0.2 m projection

Front view

0.075 m projection

0.1 m projection

0.2 m projection

Side view

Figure 18. The impact of different horizontal projections on flame heights, in-front and side views are shown. A reference heat-release rate of 47 kW (1 g/s) was applied for all projection lengths. The flames shown in these figures are pure gas flames (no ignition on board surface).

Figure 18 illustrates how three different-sized horizontal projections affected flame heights and flow distribution at the same heat-release rate. The 0.075 m and 0.1 m projections resulted in higher flame heights as the flames spread more directly upward with minimal obstruction. On the other hand, the longer 0.2 m projection caused a wider flame to spread below the projection. This allowed the flames to disperse in all directions and reduced the vertical flame height. The 0.2 m projection deflected the flame outward to a larger extent and reduced continuous contact with the board surface, compared with the 0.075 and 0.1 m projections.

Figure 19. (a) Flame height as a function of time at different fire phases, (b) The graph illustrates flame heights over 600 s exposure time for 0.075 m, 0.1 m, and 0.2 m horizontal projections at 47 kW heat-release rate (data shown here represent a 5-point moving average for all projections).

Figure 19 (a) displays flame heights at different fire phases during an experiment. Three separate curves in Figure 19 (b) represent the flame heights for 0.075 m, 0.1 m, and 0.2 m projections at 47 kW heat-release rate. Flame heights were lower, and minimal variations can be observed for 0.2 m projection. No ignition occurred due to limited heat transfer to the board surface. In contrast, significant fluctuations were observed for both 0.075 m and 0.1 m projections, and this eventually facilitated ignition. However, this study only explored 0.2 m projection for a single heat-release rate (47 kW) but still demonstrated the influence of longer projection in vertical fire spread.

5.2 Flame heights along the wall

The graphs in [Figures 20 & 21](#) depict the flame heights (H_f) over time for six different heat-release rates (33 kW, 37 kW, 42 kW, 47 kW, 51 kW, and 56 kW) with different horizontal projections (0.1 m and 0.075 m). Data for each conducted experiment is plotted along with averaged values. Additional data for 33 kW and 47 kW fires with 0.05 m and 0.2 m horizontal projections are also presented in [Figure 22](#). For lower heat-release rates (33 - 42 kW), no significant fluctuations in flame heights were observed with the 0.1 m projection within 10 min (600 s) duration (see [Figure 20](#)). Flame heights were between 0.25 m and 0.47 m at 33 kW heat-release rate. For the 0.075 m projection, at same fire size, flame heights ranged between 0.28 m and 0.55 m. At 37 kW fire, flame heights with 0.1 m projection fluctuated between 0.23 m and 0.49 m. But with 0.075 m projection flame heights peaked above 1 m after 9.5 min in second and third experiments. Such increases in flame heights occurred with both 0.1 m and 0.075 m projections after 7.4 min and 4.3 min at 42 kW fire, respectively. The steep increase in flame heights indicated ignition on the board surface. However, the 0.1 m projection resulted in reduced flame heights at lower heat-release rates compared with the 0.075 m projection because the longer projection increased the flame's travel distance before impinging on board. The flame heights considered before ignition at the board were pure gas flame heights and maintained steady fluctuations.

At higher heat-release rates (47–56 kW), flame height fluctuations were more noticeable, but the differences in flame heights between the 0.1 m and 0.075 m projections became less distinct (see [Figure 21](#)). At 47 kW heat-release rate, both projections resulted in higher flame heights, with average peak heights ranging from 0.98 m to 1.09 m. The 0.1 m projection showed more variation in flame height across repetitions compared with the 0.075 m projection. A gradual decrease in flame heights was observed with the 0.075 m projection after 7.8 min at 47 kW fire. As the heat-release rate increased to 51 kW, the flame heights for both projections continued to increase at fully developed fire but then stabilized. The difference between the flame heights of the two projections reduced further. With 0.075 m projection, averaged flame height reached up to 1.5 meters, while the 0.1 m projection peaked slightly below that. At the highest heat-release rate of 56 kW, both projections showed a similar pattern, with a decrease in flame heights after reaching their peak. The peak heights were comparable, around 1.18 to 1.2 meters. The variation between projection sizes diminished at this intensity.

Karyaparambil et al. [9] observed longer steady-state flame heights after declination from the peak. Experimental durations were up to 25 min and no horizontal projection was used in any cases. This would have led to faster ignition and the flame heights could be sustained over the charred board through continuous fuel flow. However, in this current study, when a horizontal projection was applied, greater disparities in flame heights and burning characteristics were observed within 10 min experimental duration.

Figure 20. Flame heights (H_f) plotted as a function of time. Labels (a) to (f) represent flame heights with 0.1 m (a, c, e) and 0.075 m (b, d, f) projections at 33, 37, and 42 kW heat-release rate. Data from each experiment is presented here together with averaged values. A 5-second moving average was applied to reduce noise.

Figure 21. Flame heights (H_f) over time for 0.1 m and 0.075 m projections at 47, 51, and 56 kW heat-release rates. A 5-second moving average was applied to smooth the data and reduce noise.

Three experiments with 0.05 m horizontal projections were conducted at 33 kW fire for 10 min. Flame heights varied between 0.25 m and 0.58 m. A single experiment with a 0.2 m projection at 47 kW heat-release rate was also conducted. Steady-state flame heights were observed along the wall, with a maximum value of 0.48 m (as shown in [Figure 22](#)).

Figure 22. Flame heights (H_f) for 0.05 m and 0.2 m projections, respectively at 33, and 47 kW heat-release rates over 10 min experimental duration. Data were averaged over 5 data points throughout each experiment (5-sec moving average).

Averaged flame heights for all projection lengths are plotted together in [Figure 23 \(a-f\)](#). A clear transition can be observed in terms of flame heights as projection length and heat-release rates varied. The differences in flame heights between two projections (0.1 m and 0.075 m) are noticeable up to 42 kW, but from 47 kW onwards to 56 kW, these differences gradually reduce. Above 42 kW fire, the projections were less effective in suppressing fire spread along the vertical wall. Averaged flame heights with 0.05 m and 0.2 m projections are also presented in [Figure 23](#) for 33 kW and 47 kW fires.

Figure 23. Flame heights ($H_{f,avg}$) for different projection lengths at the same heat-release rates plotted as a function of time. The data shown here have been averaged over three experiments for 0.1 m projection and two for 0.075 m projection. Data for the 0.05 m and 0.2 m projections are shown for the 33 kW and 47 kW fires only.

5.2.1 Venting flame distance (flame height + projection length)

In Figure 24, the venting flame distance (averaged flame height + projection length) at different heat-release rates is compared. Figure 24 (a) shows averaged values for the cases without ignition on the board (only gas flame heights), while Figure 24 (b) shows those after ignition (flames on board contributed to the heights). The 0.1 m projection experiment did not ignite at 33 and 37 kW fires, and the 0.075 m projection prevented ignition at 33 kW, so Figure 24 (b) does not include these heat-release rates. Before ignition, the values for both projections were nearly equal and linearly increased with heat-release rates. A disparity in total heights between the 0.1 m and 0.075 m projections was observed at 42 kW fire. It has occurred because the 0.075 m projection caused faster ignition than the 0.1 m projection. This resulted in longer flame exposure and steeper flame heights (see Figure 23 c). With increase in heat-release rates, the disparity was reduced, and at 56 kW fire, both projections provided almost identical values.

Figure 24. Flame height + projection length at different heat-release rates, (a) Before ignition on board (only gas flame heights, no contribution of board ignition), (b) After ignition on board. The flame height values were averaged over all conducted experiments for a given value of heat-release rate.

5.3 Ignition on board surface

The ignition time was determined using camera footage (detailed in section 4.3). Figure 25 (a-b) shows the ignition times for all experiments conducted with 0.1 m and 0.075 m projections at various heat-release rates. In Figure 25 (c), averaged ignition times for both projections with standard deviations are plotted together.

The 0.1 m projection successfully prevented ignition at 33 and 37 kW heat-release rates during the 10 min experiments. Experiments were conducted three times. An additional experiment was run separately at 33 kW for 20 min, also in this case, no ignition was observed. Similarly, 0.075 m projection prevented ignition in two experimental attempts at 33 kW fire. At 37 kW, no ignition occurred in the first experiment, but the second and third experiments recorded ignition at 9.4 min and 9.85 min with 0.075 m projection, respectively. Gas flames at 33 and 37 kW fires weren't sufficient to transfer heat to the wall surpassing the projections. Furthermore, no ignition was noticed with the 0.05 m projection at 33 kW fire for 10 min during three consecutive experiments.

Figure 25. Ignition time for, (a) 0.1 m, and (b) 0.075 m projections at different heat-release rates (33 - 56 kW). Data from all conducted experiments have been plotted, (c) Averaged ignition times with standard deviations are plotted for both projections. Ignition times with a value of 0 indicate that no ignition was observed at those heat-release rates.

As the heat-release rate increased, the deflection capacity of the projections was overpowered by the flame intensity. The 0.1 m projection delayed ignition compared with the 0.075 m projection at the same heat-release rates. Furthermore, a 0.2 m longer projection prevented ignition on the board at 47 kW fire, while the 0.1 m and 0.075 m projections ignited around 5.4 min and 4.25 min on average at same the heat-release rate. Similar observations showed that the deeper or longer the projection, the more it delayed ignition on the wooden façade [17]. At 56 kW heat-release rate, the ignition times for the 0.075 m and 0.1 m projections were similar (Figure 25 c). With both projections, ignition occurred between 1.8 min and 2.2 min in all experiments.

5.4 Sideward plume spread beneath the projection

The current study did not facilitate such a medium to observe flame spreading beneath the horizontal projection. However, expressions from the reference study [36] (detailed in section 2.1.2) can be adapted to calculate and compare sideward plume spread or flame extension beneath the projection with data from the current study. Current study differs from the reference

Figure 26. (a) Plume extension length under the horizontal projection compared with current study and reference study [36], (b) Adapted correlation with current experimental values at 0.1 and 0.075 m projections. The reference study used several projections at different opening dimensions, but only values with 0.1 m projection were extracted to maintain relevance with the current study.

studies in terms of the position of horizontal projection and opening dimensions. The flame extension lengths beneath the projection, R_f were calculated using the adapted equations 4 to 8 (mentioned in the section 2.1.2). The lower 33 kW and 37 kW heat-release rates weren't considered here to maintain relevance with reference study. [Figure 26 \(a\)](#) compares the calculated flame extension lengths beneath the projection with the data reported in Lu et al.'s [\[36\]](#) study. Lu et al. found that the horizontal projection over the compartment window or opening should be larger than the R_f value to reduce the vertical fire damage. [Figure 26 \(b\)](#) demonstrates a non-dimensional correlation based on current study with 0.1 m and 0.075 m horizontal projections under different heat-release rates (42-56 kW).

5.5 Vertical temperature profile

Figures 27 and 28 represent temperature profiles on board surface (vertical heights from 0.1 m to 0.9 m) with 0.1 and 0.075 m horizontal projections across six different heat-release rates (from 33 kW to 56 kW) over 10 min durations. Temperature data at every 3 sec intervals have been averaged from multiple repeated experiments (three experiments with 0.1 m projection and two with 0.075 m projection). At 33 kW fire steady state temperatures can be observed ranged between 100 °C and 250 °C over the board heights for both 0.1 m and 0.075 m projections. Temperature plateau ranged between 75 °C and 290 °C at 37 kW fire over the experimental period with 0.1 m projection. But steep temperature rise above 450 °C was observed with 0.075 m projection at same heat-release rate, close to end of the experiment. This steep rise in vertical temperatures indicated ignition on board. At 42 kW fire both horizontal projections provided sharp temperatures rise between 7 to 9.5 min for the 0.1 m projection and 4.3 to 6.3 min for the 0.075 m projection. Among the thermocouples placed along the board height, peak temperatures (exceeding 700 °C) were recorded by those positioned between 0.1 m and 0.3 m height at 42 kW fire.

Figure 27. Gas temperatures along board heights for 0.1 m horizontal projection plotted as a function of time. The legends 0.1 to 0.9 representing the thermocouple heights along the façade. (Temperature data at 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, and 0.9 m heights are shown to minimize noise. Data with 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8 m are provided in [Appendix: C](#)).

Figure 28. Gas temperatures at different heights for 0.075 m horizontal projection plotted as a function of time. The legends 0.1 to 0.9 m representing the thermocouple heights along the façade.

At 47 kW, peak temperatures reached over 720 °C between 7.8 and 8 min with 0.1 horizontal projection. A plateau phase with temperatures ranging from 530 °C to 550 °C was observed before peaking. At 51 kW and 56 kW, peak temperatures exceeded 750 °C at lower heights, but vertical temperature development was faster at 56 kW than at 51 kW with the 0.1 m projection. Similarly, with the 0.075 m projection, peak temperatures were recorded between 750 °C and 780 °C at lower thermocouple heights for 47 to 56 kW heat-release rates. At greater board heights (0.7 m to 0.9 m), temperatures remained lower, peaking around 500 °C. As shown in the graphs (Figure 27 & 28), vertical temperature development was faster with the 0.075 m projection compared with the 0.1 m projection at all heat-release rates except 56 kW. At 56 kW, the disparity between both projections reduced.

Figure 29 shows the average gas temperatures along the board and temperatures at 0.006 m depths for all horizontal projections (0.2, 0.1, 0.075, and 0.05 m) at heat-release rates from 33 to 56 kW. All temperature data are plotted together for a clearer comparison and better understanding of the variations across different projections.

Figure 29. Temperatures with different projections at various heat-release rates (kW) are shown. Data have been averaged from all experiments for each projection length and fire size, then plotted together along the 0.1 m to 0.9 m board height. The horizontal line separates the gas temperature data from the data 0.006 m inside the board. Additionally, 0.05 m and 0.2 m projections were used for 33 kW and 47 kW fires.

5.6 Charring properties on fire exposed particle board

5.6.1 Char depth measurements from the cross-section of cut panels

Wooden particle board is a heterogeneous material with varying density and composition, which makes the charring process complex due to uneven heat distribution and localized (non-uniform) pyrolysis [50]. The thickness of the boards used in this study was 0.012 m (12 mm). Heat penetration time was calculated to be approximately 4.4 min, based on the properties of the board and exposure to a one-dimensional heat source [51].

Deformation of particle boards was noticed at the end of the experiments, particularly in boards that experienced ignition. The degree of deformation increased with fire sizes. Areas with intense charring, especially at the lower end charred boards showed more variation in deformation. Char depths (in mm) were measured twice from the contour images of the cross-section panels and then averaged (as shown in Figure 30). However, the measurement system did not consider missing char from the cut panels during the cutting or handling of the charred particle boards. The detailed analysis of char depth measurement system described in 4.2.3 section. Also, the deformed board pictures are provided in Appendix: D.

Figure 30. Averaged char depths for 0.1 m and 0.075 m projections at several heat-release rates (kW). Char depth values for two measurement attempts are plotted along with their averaged values. The depths were averaged across the board heights at each corresponding heat-release rate for every measurement.

Figure 31 illustrates the char depths (in mm) of the direct flame impingement zone (0.1 m to 0.4 m along board height) for 0.1 and 0.075 m projections at different heat-release rates. The

zone representing the char depths (d_{char}) covers area of 0.18 m^2 ($1.8 \times 10^5 \text{ mm}^2$), where each cell covers 0.005 m^2 ($5 \times 10^3 \text{ mm}^2$) of total board area. The direct flame impingement zone was assumed to receive maximum flame exposure and heat flux for a given exposure duration and heat-release rates. No char data at 33 and 37 kW fires with 0.1 m projections is present as no ignition on board was observed with these fires. Similar with 0.075 m projection at 33 kW fire. [Figure 31](#) shows the char depths (d_{char}) at direct flame impingement zone increased with heat-release rate for both projections. The difference in char depths at 37 kW and 42 kW is more prominent with 0.1 m projection compared with the 0.075 m projection. However, from 47 kW to 56 kW, the differences in char depths between two projections were reduced, indicating a convergence in the impact of the projections at higher fire intensities.

Figure 31. Measured char depths (d_{char}) at the direct flame impingement zone (0.1 m to 0.4 m of board height) on the board surface for 0.1 and 0.075 m projections and several heat-release rates. The depths values in this zone covers 0.18 m^2 ($1.8 \times 10^5 \text{ mm}^2$) area of the board.

[Figure 32](#) illustrates the average char depths along the board height for various heat-release rates. For the 0.1 m projection, average char depths at 42 kW fire measured the lowest, ranging from $0.45 \pm 0.07 \text{ mm}$ to $4.33 \pm 0.93 \text{ mm}$. The maximum depths were observed at 56 kW fire, measuring from $0.76 \pm 0.23 \text{ mm}$ to $6.51 \pm 1.56 \text{ mm}$. Similarly, for the 0.075 m projection, the lowest depth was measured at 37 kW fire, ranging from 0.43 mm to $3.4 \pm 0.91 \text{ mm}$, while the maximum char depth at 56 kW fire measured from $0.67 \pm 0.57 \text{ mm}$ to $6.02 \pm 1.55 \text{ mm}$. Variation in depth developments at the lower edge of the board is visible from [Figure 32](#).

It can be expected that char depths decrease uniformly along with the board height when subjected to direct flame contact. The complexity arose due to the horizontal projection altered the uniform flow pattern of flame. A gap was created due to a low- pressure vortex formation at the edge and heat exposure wasn't evenly distributed.

Figure 32. Average char depths ($d_{char.avg}$) at various heat-release rates and horizontal projections are plotted against the vertical board heights. The char depths were averaged across the board's width at 50 mm intervals along the height for each corresponding projection and heat-release rate.

5.6.2 Charring rate based on char depth

Charring rate (mm/min) is a crucial quantity for wood or wood-based products in terms of fire resistance calculations for timber structures. The charring rates in this study were calculated from the measured char depth results. Several studies [52][53] have indicated that wood thermally decomposes into char at temperatures $\sim 280-300$ °C when exposed to heat. A higher charring rate generally indicates faster degradation of material. Figure 33 shows the charring rates at different heat-release rates and projections (0.1 and 0.075 m). Charring rates were calculated using two approaches, the first was based on the average char depths at each specific heat-release rate, and the second was derived from the char depth values within the direct

flaming zone (between 0.1 m and 0.4 m of the board height). The charring rate increased with fire sizes for both projections. With 0.1 m projection, the average charring rate at 42 kW was calculated the lowest 0.24 mm/min, and the highest calculated 0.33 mm/min at 56 kW fire. At direct flaming zone the lowest rate was 0.34 mm/min and maximum were 0.5 mm/min for same fire sizes. With 0.075 m projection the lowest charring rate observed 0.16 mm/min at 37 kW fire, as ignition started at this heat-release rate. At direct flaming zone the rate was 0.18 mm/min at same fire size. For 56 kW fire, average rate calculated 0.35 mm/min and 0.54 mm/min at direct flaming zone.

Martinka et al. [53] investigated char depths and charring rates of Norway spruce and scots pine using cone calorimeter and found charring rate increased with heat flux and decreased with longer flame exposure. The average charring rate was 0.73–1.5 mm/min for spruce wood and 0.67–1.3 mm/min for pine wood. The calculated charring rate varied from 0.51 to 0.62 mm/min for glue-laminated woods at different exposure times (60 – 120 min) [54].

Figure 33. Charring rates (mm/min) for 0.1 and 0.075 m projections at various heat-release rates. Charring rates calculated from overall depth values and averaged for particular heat-release rate. Averaged charring rates at direct flame impingement zone also plotted together for both projections. Charring rates at 37 kW fire plotted only with 0.075 m projection, as with 0.1 m projection no char formed on board.

Karyaparambil et al. [9] observed charring rate at maximum depth increased by 0.09 mm/min with every 4-5 kW increase in heat-release rate and stabilized around 0.65 mm/min. None of these studies didn't include any projection against the venting flame or similar approach. However, the current study observed that each 4-5 kW increase in heat-release rate led to an average increase in charring rate of 0.03 mm/min for the 0.1 m projection and 0.05 mm/min for the 0.075 m projection at 10 min flame exposure.

5.6.3 Char height, char area and char volume

Char heights, H_{char} were noticeably influenced by the horizontal projections at different heat-release rates. In Figure 34, both the visible and measured char heights are plotted for each projection. The visible char heights were averaged from corresponding experiments at each heat-release rate, with standard deviations. Measured char heights were based on the minimum char depth recorded vertically along the board.

The difference in char height between 0.1 and 0.075 m projections was acute at 42 kW fire. With 0.075 m projection, both visible and measured char heights were greater than with 0.1 m

Figure 34. Char heights (H_{char}) for both projections at various heat-release rates are plotted. Visible char heights were determined based on blister or crack formation on the board surface, while measured data represent the least detectable char depth on the board. Standard deviations are included for the visible char height data. No char formation was observed with the 0.1 m projection at the 37 kW fire.

projection during the 10 min experiments. As, 0.1 m projection significantly delayed ignition (avg.- 8.8 min) on board at this heat-release rate compared with 0.075 m projection (avg.- 5.3 min). Consequently, char formation was limited within the 10 min duration for 0.1 m projection. But from 47 kW to 56 kW fires, no significant increase was noticed in char heights in case of projection lengths or increased heat-release rates. Difference between 0.1 and 0.075 m projections was reduced, a slower progression or steady growth in char height observed with increased heat-release rates.

However, greater variations in char heights and areas were observed when repeating the experiments under the same exposure time and heat-release rate (Figure 35). Char heights were more likely governed by the flame heights when pyrolysis front triggered by the heat transfer from upward buoyant plume. Increased heat-release rates intensified the convective flow on surface with higher flame reach.

Visible char heights (experiment no- 1, 2 & 3)
H. Projection- 0.1 m
HRR- 47 kW (1 g/s gas flow)

Visible char heights (experiment no- 1 & 2)
H. Projection- 0.075 m
HRR- 47 kW (1 g/s gas flow)

Figure 35. Variations in char height, H_{char} across different experiments and projections at the same heat-release rate. No significant differences in char heights were observed due to changes in projection sizes. The red dotted line indicates the visually observed char height on the board surface. A high-resolution contour plot distinguishing char regions is provided in [Appendix: D](#).

The char area data for the 0.1 m and 0.075 m horizontal projections demonstrate a clear pattern of growth with increasing flame intensity (as shown in Figure 36 a). Visible char areas were determined individually for each experiment and then averaged. Measurable char areas represent single experiment data based on measurable char depths. At 42 kW, the visible char area for the 0.1 m projection reached 0.12 m², while the measured char area found increased to 0.16 m². For other heat-release rates with the 0.1 m projection, the visible char area closely matched the measured area. The most notable increase occurred between 42 kW and 47 kW, where the char area doubled to 0.26 m². From 47 kW to 51 kW, the char area further increased from 0.26 m² to 0.35 m². Stabilization with slight increase in char area to 0.38 m² was noticed at 56 kW fire.

Figure 36. (a) Char area (in m²), (b) Char volume (in m³) plotted for different heat-release rates. Visible and measured char areas are plotted together for 0.1 and 0.075 m projections. Char volumes were calculated from average char depths and areas for corresponding fire size.

For the 0.075 m projection, a similar trend was observed, starting from a char area of 0.08 m² at 37 kW and significantly rising to 0.22 m² at 42 kW. At 56 kW fire char area maximized to 0.41 m², which was 0.03 m² increase from 0.1 m projection at same heat-release rate. No significant differences were observed in vertical char development between the 0.1 m and 0.075 m projection. However, increased charring along the board width was noticed with the 0.075 m projection compared with 0.1 m projection.

Char volumes were calculated from the averaged char depth data and char area for individual heat-release rates. In [Figure 36 b](#), both visible and measured char volumes for both projections are shown in m^3 . With 0.1 m horizontal projection, average char volume increased by $6.5 \times 10^{-3} m^3$ at every 4-5 kW increase in heat-release rate. With 0.075 m projection the average char volume increased by $7.3 \times 10^{-3} m^3$.

5.7 Mass loss and moisture regain in boards

The particle boards were weighed three times for individual experiment [Figure 37 \(a\)](#). Before the start of the experiment, after 1 hour of experiment and after 24 hours of experiment. [Figure 37 \(b\)](#) shows the mass loss% of boards from the weights after 1 hour of experiment. With 0.1 m projection, the mass loss% after 1 hour increased with the heat-release rates. At 37 kW, there was a minimal mass loss of around 1.04%, while at higher heat-release rates, 51 kW and 56 kW, the mass loss became more pronounced, reaching approximately 12.4% and 13.2%, respectively. A similar trend was observed with 0.075 m projection, where the lowest mass loss was around 1.4% at 37 kW fire and the highest at 56 kW, approx. 14.7%. Greater heat exposures led to a higher rate of mass loss due to more intense thermal decomposition or moisture evaporation. The graph shows a clear proportional and linear relationship between mass loss% and heat-release rate for both projection lengths, where the slope of each line representing the rate of increase.

[Figure 37 \(c\)](#) represents mass regain% after 24 hours of experiment. After a 24-hour period, there was a slight mass regain, attributed to moisture absorption from the surrounding environment. This regain was generally less than 1.5% across all heat-release rates for both projections. Boards at lower heat-release rates experienced minimal mass loss, and that led to relatively lower moisture regain. Intense fires caused more irreversible charring and material loss that limited the board's capacity to reabsorb moisture.

The mass loss of particle boards occurred due to the combination of moisture evaporation and combustion of the boards. Moisture evaporation contributed to mass loss at initial heat-release rates where the boards did not ignite. However, at higher heat-release rates, the majority of the mass loss resulted due to combustion. The increased mass loss observed at heat-release rates between 42-56 kW fires indicated a transition from moisture-driven loss to material degradation caused by pyrolysis and oxidation.

Figure 37. (a) Measured weights of the particle board were recorded at three separate intervals (reference heat-release rate- 56 kW, reference projection- 0.1 m), (b) Mass loss% of particle boards after 1 hr of experiment, (c) Mass regain% after 24 hr of experiment, for 0.1 m and 0.075 m projections across all heat-release rates. Values were averaged across all experiments for each specific projection and fire size. These regain values were based on weights measured 24 hours post-experiment and could have varied with extended timeframes, such as measurements taken after 30 days or 365 days.

Chapter 6

Discussion

6.1 Comparative analysis of flame heights with and without horizontal projection

Flame heights indicate the intensity of heat transfer to the wall. Upward-venting flames naturally follow the upward buoyant plume path, and when there is a wall, flames tend to attach to the wall due to the Coandă effect [48]. The attachment of the flame to the wall increases convective heat transfer between the flames and the wall, increasing the surface temperature and the likelihood of ignition. Horizontal projections over the compartment opening altered the path of flames by deflecting outward rather than continuing directly along the board. A gap formed between the flames and the board, resulting in flame height reduction. Due to lower flame heights, continuous contact of flames with the board surface was disrupted. This event reduced the heat transfer from the flames to the wall, both radiatively and convectively. As the projections became longer or deeper, the degree of disruption increased. The graphs in [Figure 22](#) highlight the effectiveness of longer projection in reducing flame heights even at more intense fire. The 0.05 m projection at 33 kW maintained steady flame heights, while the longer (0.2 m) projection achieved a similar plateau despite the higher heat-release rate of 47 kW.

A comparison of flame heights as a function of time is shown in [Figure 38](#). Data from similar studies [9][10] without horizontal projections are plotted alongside data from the current study. Data for 10 min of experimental duration have been considered to ensure compatibility with the current study. The comparison clearly demonstrates that the use of horizontal projections resulted in lower flame heights at the same heat-release rates (33 kW & 37 kW) compared with scenarios without projections. The 0.1 m, 0.075 m, and 0.05 m projections, which were approximately 1/4th, 1/5th, and 1/8th the size of the opening length, reduced the average flame heights by 29% to 45% compared with no projections at 33 kW fire. At 37 kW fire, reduction was noticed from 33% to 44% with 0.1 and 0.075 m projections. Flame heights in [Figure 38](#) with 0.1, 0.075 and 0.05 m projections are pure gas flames, as no ignition was noticed at the wall (except with 0.075 m projection at 37 kW fire). In the reference studies [9][10], the rapid rise in flame height curves illustrates ignition on the board surface between 2.4 and 3 min.

Figure 38. Averaged flame heights (H_f) are compared between the current study's experimental data and data from other studies without projection [9][10]. Despite of differences in experimental parameters, the 33 and 37 kW data could be directly compared with current study. The data from these studies have been extracted and adjusted to compare. This comparison aimed to highlight the impact of horizontal projections on flame heights, as the other studies did not use any.

6.2 Thermal analysis

6.2.1 Temperature distribution at the onset of ignition

Any horizontal projection (e.g., balcony, canopy, eave) plays a crucial role in influencing the movement direction and temperature distribution during upward façade flame spread. Horizontal projections were especially effective at lower heat-release rates (33–42 kW fires), as the gas flow or flame intensity remained lower and could be deflected more easily by the projection over the compartment. However, at higher heat-release rates (47–56 kW), high-velocity plumes tended to overpower the deflecting effect of the projections. Although the peak temperatures for the heat-release rates ranged from 680 °C to 790 °C, ignition on the board surface varied, with higher heat-release rates leading to faster ignition. Figure 39 shows temperatures at 0.2 m height of the board for both projections (0.1 m and 0.075 m), as thermocouples at this height recorded the highest temperatures during the experiments. The ignition temperatures at this height ranged from 300 °C to 415 °C for both projections at corresponding heat-release rates. Fangrat, Hasemi et al. [55] studied ignition temperatures for several plyboards of variable thickness and density. They observed that rapid exothermic oxidation on wood-based boards occurs between 297 °C and 397 °C.

Figure 39. Temperatures at 0.2 m height at the particle board for different heat-release rates and projections. The first graph represents the temperatures with the 0.1 m projection, while the second shows temperatures for the 0.075 m projection. The temperature range at the time of ignition is marked with dotted lines.

Additionally, the modulus of elasticity for wood-based materials begins to decrease at temperatures above 200 °C and fully decomposes between 380 °C and 500 °C [56]. After ignition on the board, temperature development followed a similar trend across all higher heat-release rates (47 kW, 51 kW, and 56 kW) for both 0.1 m and 0.075 m horizontal projections. As expected, the 0.1 m projection delayed ignition compared with the 0.075 m projection. However, the differences shortened at higher heat-release rates. At 51 and 56 kW fires, the ignition time difference for both projections became minimal. The increased fuel flow intensified the upward buoyant plume, increasing temperatures and reducing the projections' influence at higher heat-release rates. Continuous flame contact with the surface accelerated convective heat transfer to the board. In contrast, a longer projection (0.2 m) interrupted the heat transfer and prevented ignition at 47 kW heat-release rate.

Despite differences in ignition timing, post-ignition temperature behaviour remained similar across all heat-release rates. Temperatures peaked after ignition and plateaued following char formation on the board surface. This behaviour indicated that once ignition occurred, thermal development on the board surface stabilized until the gas flow stopped, regardless of the heat-release rate.

6.2.2 Pre-ignition gas temperature comparison with and without horizontal projection

A comparative analysis between the results of the current study and similar external fire studies (without horizontal projections) is presented in Figure 40. Data from the reference studies [9][10] were extracted specifically for 33 and 37 kW fires to compare directly with the current study with projections. Vertical gas temperature data before ignition on wall are represented here for all studies. At 33 kW, inclusion of horizontal projections reduced vertical temperatures by approximately 39% with the 0.05 m projection, 46% with the 0.075 m projection, and 52% with the 0.1 m projection compared with conditions without projections. The temperature reductions for the 37 kW fire ranged from 47% to 56% with 0.075 m and 0.1 m projections.

The lower gas temperature was observed as all horizontal projections were able to deflect flames and reduced heat transfer to the wall compared with no projections. The degree of deflection and temperature reduction increased with projection lengths.

The current study also found that a 0.2 m horizontal projection has a significant reduction in vertical temperature profiles (see Figure 29). Three horizontal projections (0.2 m, 0.1 m, and 0.075 m) at 47 kW HRR indicated an average reduction in vertical temperatures of 3.16% from 0.075 m to 0.1 m and an average reduction of 56% from 0.1 m to 0.2 m. The difference was substantial, as longer projection (0.2 m) significantly limited the heat transfer to the board.

Figure 40. Comparison of average gas temperatures along the board height with and without horizontal projection. Gas temperature data before ignition on the board surface were derived from reference studies (no H. projection) [9][10] since no ignition was observed with horizontal projections on the board surface at these referred heat-release rates (33 and 37 kW).

6.2.3 Thermal depth and moisture evaporation inside the board

Figure 41 presents the temperature development over time at a depth of 0.006 m inside the particle board, measured at the height of 0.2 m, for both the 0.1 m and 0.075 m horizontal projections. Temperatures at this specific height were plotted to minimize noise that could result from including data across all heights. At this height (0.2 m) along the board, the highest overall temperatures were recorded over experimental durations.

The thermal penetration depth into the board at corresponding heat-release rates can be predicted from internal temperature development. At 33, 37, and 42 kW fires, temperatures plateaued below 100 °C with the 0.1 m projection (Figure 41 a). A similar plateau occurred at 33 and 37 kW with the 0.075 m projection (Figure 41 b). This plateau likely occurred because the heat energy was primarily absorbed for moisture evaporation within the board. Around 100 °C, moisture in the wood begins to evaporate, requiring latent heat for the phase transition from liquid to vapor. This process temporarily delayed further temperature rise inside the board [51].

As the heat-release rate increased, more intense heat energy conducted from the surface penetrated deeper into the board, accelerating internal temperature development. At 47, 51, and 56 kW fires, temperatures inside the board (at 0.006 m depth) increased more rapidly,

particularly with the 0.075 m projection. Faster thermal penetration led to quicker moisture evaporation and a steeper rise in internal temperatures compared with the 0.1 m projection.

Figure 41. Temperatures at 0.006 m (0.6 cm) inside the board at 0.2 m vertical height for different heat-release rates with (a) 0.1 m, and (b) 0.075 m projections. Only the temperatures at 0.2 m height have been plotted to reduce the noise that could occur from displaying all the data together.

6.2.4 Char depth and temperatures inside the board

Figure 42 illustrates char depths (mm) and temperatures at 0.006 m (6 mm) inside the particle board for various heat-release rates. Char depth and temperature data were averaged along 0.1 m to 0.4 m (100 mm to 400 mm) board height, previously identified as the direct flame impingement zone. Temperatures were considered from the time ignition occurred on the board until the end of each experiment.

Char depth increased with heat-release rates for both projections. The 0.1 m projection slowed the progression of char depth compared with 0.075 m projection due to its longer deflection length, as expected. From the temperatures (0.1 m to 0.4 m height) recorded at 0.006 m depth, it was observed that, at 37 and 42 kW fires, the board remained in the drying phase, delaying further temperature development. Furthermore, Charring on surface acted as an insulator, reducing heat transfer to inner depths at these heat-release rates.

At higher fire intensities (47–56 kW), the thermal behaviour shifted towards the pre-pyrolysis phase. After moisture evaporation, the exothermic dehydration phase began above 100 °C, followed by the primary pyrolysis reaction over 200 °C, which produced primary char [50].

Figure 42. Averaged temperatures (0.006 m inside the board) after ignition on the board plotted against averaged char depth at various heat-release rates. Both char depth and temperature data represented data from 0.1 m to 0.4 m board heights. The vertical dashed line represents the thermocouples position, which were 0.006 m (6 mm) inside the board, and the horizontal dashed line represents the boiling point of water. (a) Graph representing data with 0.1 m projection, (b) Graph representing data with 0.075 m projection, and (c) Visual representation of thermocouple data considered here from 0.1 m to 0.4 m along the board.

6.3 Analysis of heat flux density using calculative method

The horizontal projections (0.1 m and 0.075 m) used in this study were $1/4^{\text{th}}$ and $1/5^{\text{th}}$ of the height of the compartment opening. The heat flux densities along the board have been calculated from the temperature data recorded at various heights. No system was developed to measure heat flux along the board. Although this calculative approach has limitations, the approximate heat flux densities can be predicted. Radiative and convective heat flux densities were combined to determine the total heat flux at different heights. The heat transfer coefficient was assumed to be constant throughout the whole exposure time. Both Law's [22] and Oleskiewicz's [11] methods were considered for determining this coefficient. Figure 43 represents the calculated heat flux densities for both projection lengths (heat transfer coefficient calculated from Law's equation). Averaged flame heights are also plotted along the right Y axis for better visual representation. Examples of calculation stages and comparative analysis of average heat flux densities (heat transfer coefficient calculated based on Oleskiewicz and Law) are detailed in Appendix: E.

For lower heat-release rates (33 kW, 37 kW, 42 kW), an increasing buoyancy effect was observed along the projection lengths. The upward driven buoyant flames exhibited difficulty in maintaining constant contact with the particle board, possibly due to the projection length causing the flames to deflect outward and broke their direct path along the surface. Additionally, side winds from both directions further pushed the deflected flames away from the board, reducing the likelihood of continuous flame attachment. Noticeable differences in heat flux densities at different heights with 0.1 m and 0.075 m projections can be observed in these heat-release rates (as shown in Figure 43). The heat flux densities remained relatively low and stable across all heights.

At higher heat-release rates (47 kW, 51 kW, 56 kW), flames adhered to the board surface more effectively. The heat flux to the wall increased proportionally with the heat-release rates. The radiative heat flux along the board did not significantly impact the total heat flux, whereas convective heat flux densities were calculated considerably higher. At lower heat-release rates, flames experienced greater heat loss to the surroundings via radiation after being deflected by the projection. Radiant heat flux densities were nearly zero at 0.7 m and 0.9 m heights until ignition occurred on the board. However, at 47 kW and above, heat flux densities also increased at these upper heights (0.7 m and 0.9 m board height) after ignition for both projections. Flame heights were higher and propagated radically. The highest flux values were typically observed between 0.1 m and 0.4 m along the board, previously termed the direct flame impingement zone. Overall, total heat flux density increased with higher heat-release rates but gradually decreased along the height of the board.

(a)

(b)

Figure 43. Heat flux densities at different heights for (a) 0.1 m, and (b) 0.075 m horizontal projections are plotted as a function of time. The average flame heights corresponding to the reference heat-release rates are also shown on the right Y-axis. The calculated heat flux density data along the board height (0.1 m, 0.3 m, 0.5 m, 0.7 m, and 0.9 m) are represented with dotted lines. Calculated heat flux presented here considered Law's heat transfer coefficient equation.

Oleszkiewicz [11] applied a 1.22 m deep flame deflector or horizontal projection against a window-ejected wood-crib plume for 3 min. The projection significantly reduced the heat flux to the upper wall and offered greater protection. In the current study, the average reduction in heat flux densities along the board heights for 0.1 m horizontal projection ranged from 9% to 23% compared with 0.075 m projection at 33 and 37 kW heat-release rates. The maximum difference was 66% reduction observed at 42 kW fire with 0.1 m projection. At 47 kW and onwards, average heat flux density with 0.1 and 0.075 m projections overlapped each other along the board height, gradually reducing the impact of the projection.

Chapter 7

PyroSim (FDS) Modelling

7.1 Introduction

In this thesis, FDS has been particularly used to justify the effectiveness and impact of horizontal projections on fire spread along the exterior vertical walls of tall buildings. While the experimental studies conducted involved small-scale tests on particle boards, the simulations were designed to mimic large-scale experimental results. Large-scale fire experiments would be very challenging to replicate in real life, both practically and financially. Therefore, the simulation approach was utilized to explore outcomes on a larger scale with varying configurations of horizontal projections, which would be difficult to perform experimentally.

Vertical temperature profiles at different projection lengths and geometries have been modelled in this study. The outputs from the simulation can be questioned when compared with real-life scenarios. But also, numerical simulation studies have been systematically refined over the years to provide valuable insights. Particularly in scenarios involving large-scale fire behaviour, complex geometries, or high-risk environments where full-scale experiments are not feasible. The reliability of FDS results depends heavily on the accuracy of input data and the assumptions made in the model, which are normally based on real-life situations or experimental findings. FDS serves as a crucial tool in this research, enabling comprehensive analysis of fire dynamics in scenarios that would be very costly and complex to study solely through experimental means. PyroSim 6.7.9 and Smokeview 6.9.3 software have been used in this study to simulate different scenarios. PyroSim is a graphical user interface for Fire Dynamics Simulation (FDS) and a powerful fire simulator developed at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) [57].

7.2 Simulation set-up and model configuration

7.2.1 Building geometry

The building model used in the simulation represented a three-storey structure with a total height of 7.5 meters and a width of 3 meters. The wall thickness was set to 0.1 meters. Each floor featured a window or opening with dimensions of 0.9 meters \times 0.9 meters, positioned 0.83 meters above the floor. Flames from the compartment vented externally through these

openings. Horizontal projections were placed at 0.83 meters above each window, with a thickness of 0.1 meters. The lengths of these horizontal projections varied while the solid

(a)

(b)

Figure 44. (a) Building geometry of the simulation model, (b) Horizontal projection types, (I) Open-ended projection, (II) Projection with solid wall balustrade (0.4 m solid wall).

wall balustrade heights were consistently maintained at 0.4 meters for all projections ([Figure 44 b-II](#)). This setup was designed to assess vertical temperature profiles at different projection lengths (0.4 m, 0.6m, and 0.8 m) along the building's exterior wall. The fire source was considered in the bottom compartment. [Figure 44](#) illustrates the building geometry and the two projection types used in the simulation process.

7.2.2 Simulation geometry

The simulation domain (7.5 m × 5 m) was divided into three smaller mesh sections to enhance computational efficiency. The use of smaller meshes enabled parallel processing, which significantly reduced computation time compared with a single large mesh approach. This division allowed better utilization of computational resources, reducing the overall simulation load, graphics and time.

In total, the model consisted of 135,000 cells. Where each mesh containing 45,000 cells. The cell dimensions were 0.1 m × 0.1 m × 0.083 m to ensure consistent resolution across the simulation domain. The mesh ratio was maintained at 1.20: 1.20: 1.00, which provided a balanced distribution of computational simulation.

The boundary conditions for the outer building were set to open. The open condition allowed the flame and smoke spread freely outside of the building, simulating an open-air environment. The exterior wall surface was set inert (surface didn't contribute to generate heat). Eight thermocouples were placed along the exterior wall and each spaced 0.83 m apart to record temperatures during the simulation period. Six additional thermocouples were set 1.8 m away in the opposite direction of the thermocouples on floor- 2 and floor- 3, to observe the temperatures on the adjacent wall. Simulation time was 10 min (600 s) at every case.

The fire burner dimension was 1 m × 1 m and located centrally at the bottom compartment. The reaction type 'polyurethan_GM27' was used from the pre-stored library section. The heat-release rate per unit area (HRRPUA) was set to 3100 kW, and the surface temperature was set at 500 °C. Further details of simulation parameters are presented in [Appendix: F](#) section.

7.2.3 Analysis

FDS modelling was utilized to investigate the behaviour of flame trajectories and vertical temperature profiles. Flame vented through the lower compartment window and interacted with various horizontal projections before moving upward. The study incorporated projections of different lengths (0.4 m, 0.6 m, and 0.8 m) and two types (open-ended and with balustrades) (as shown in [Figure 44](#)). The simulations aimed to evaluate the impact of the horizontal projections on upward flame trajectory, vertical temperatures and temperatures at neighbouring

building wall. The simulation study didn't consider any results from the small scale experimental study or any reference. FDS output files were rendered in Smokeview for visualization. Also, 2D slice values were employed at $Y = 1.5$ m and $X = 1.5$ m and 4 m to visualize soot visibility, temperature, and velocity contours.

7.3 Results and discussion

7.3.1 Impact of projection types on flame trajectory

The trajectory of the ejected plume from the fire compartment window varied significantly

- **Open ended projections :**

- **Projections with solid wall balustrade:**

Figure 45. Upward flame trajectories for different projection lengths and types.

with different projection types and lengths. [Figure 45](#) illustrates the flame trajectory for various horizontal projections simulated in the Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS). Without any horizontal projection (0 m projection), the buoyant plume adhered closely to the exterior wall of the first and second floors as it rose upwards. Yokoi [7] described in his study that vertical walls restrict wind from one side while wind from the opposite direction drives the flame upward along the wall. The dimensions of the window opening also play a crucial role in the upward flame trajectory. Smaller vents tend to increase the velocity and vertical flame height. A 0.4 m open-ended horizontal projection above the fire compartment deflected the flame away from the wall. As expected, the lateral spread of the upward-moving flame increased with the length of the horizontal projection, while the vertical flame height decreased with longer projections.

Horizontal projections with solid wall balustrades produced similar impact as the open-ended projections, with the flame being deflected. But the degree of deflection was observed to be reduced compared with open-ended projections. As upward moving flame attached to the 0.4 m balustrade height before swirling over it. This may cause due to Coandă effect [48] (Detailed illustration in [Appendix: F](#)).

7.3.2 Impact of projection types on vertical temperatures

Vertical temperature profiles with horizontal projections indicated a significant declination compared with the scenario without any projection above the combustion compartment. Open-ended projections reduced temperatures by approximately 82% to 91% at 2.9 m height, and by 39% to 63% at 7.05 m. Similarly, projections with a 0.4 m solid wall balustrade reduced temperatures by up to 94% at 2.9 m and by up to 44% at 7.05 m in contrast to the values recorded with no projections (as shown in [Figure 46](#)).

Projections with solid wall balustrades exhibited greater variations in temperature profiles, with slightly higher values than open-ended projections, particularly at the higher thermocouple positions. Thermocouples at 4.6 m and 7.05 m (T5 & T8, see [Figure 44](#)), which were located immediately below the upper floor projection lengths, recorded higher temperatures than those at lower and middle positions on both floors. This could be attributed to the containment of the buoyant plume beneath the projections before deflecting or swirling over them.

Horizontal projections initially disrupted direct flame exposure to the wall by creating a gap, thereby reducing overall heat accumulation along the wall. The length and geometry of the projections influenced the degree of deflection. Longer projections resulted in slower temperature development on the exterior wall at upper floors 1 and 2. The small-scale experiments conducted in this study also observed a similar impact, where longer horizontal projections reduced vertical temperatures and delayed ignition by decreasing heat transfer to

(a)

(b)

Figure 46. Average temperatures along the wall, (a) temperatures with open-ended projections, (b) temperatures with projections featuring solid wall balustrades.

the combustible wall. Mammoser and Battaglia [2] found that rectangular balconies with open balustrades were the most effective against vertical fire spread and temperature development above. In contrast, solid wall balustrades allowed smoke and hot gases to accumulate on floors above the fire compartment. The current simulation study observed that both open-ended and solid wall balustrade projections trapped hot gases and smoke beneath them on floors above the fire compartment. Accumulation increased as projection length increased.

7.3.3 Temperature profiles on neighbouring building wall

Figure 47 shows average temperatures on neighbouring building walls located 1.8 m away from the fire-affected building. The thermocouples at the neighbouring wall were placed exactly at the same height as the fire-affected building, but 1.8 m away. The approach was to assess temperature development at neighbouring wall in case of façade fire situation. Yokoi [7] also raised a concern that horizontal projections could increase the risk of lateral fire spreading to adjacent buildings. The graph (Figure 47 b) shows the temperature values for open-ended projections, while the other graph (Figure 47 c) shows projections with solid wall balustrades. For projections with solid wall balustrades, the temperature profiles at the adjacent wall maintained an orderly development. Longer horizontal projections resulted in higher temperatures on the adjacent wall due to their increased ability to deflect the vented plume over longer distances. The upper floor-2 thermocouples recorded higher temperatures than the upper floor-1 thermocouples at 1.8 m distance.

The vertical temperatures at the adjacent wall were higher with open-ended projections compared with the projections with balustrade. The temperature development was uneven, especially for the 0.8 m open-ended projection, which provided a rapid increase on the adjacent wall. Peak temperatures of 210 °C and 196 °C were recorded at 4.6 m and 5.4 m wall height. On the other hand, fire-affected building recorded around 90 °C peak temperatures with same projection at same heights. Detailed time-based temperature profiles at each thermocouple height are presented in Appendix F.

Figure 47. Average temperatures along the wall (1.8 m away from the fire-affected building), (a) Fire-affected building with neighbouring wall, (b) Average temperatures with open-ended projections, (c) Average temperatures with projections featuring solid wall balustrades.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

8.1 Concluding remarks from the experimental study

Ignition influences flame heights, temperature profiles, and charring along the vertical combustible wall. In this study, ignition was influenced by the plume trajectory and the flame's continuous attachment to the board surface. This attachment facilitated radiative and convective heat transfer, accelerating heat transfer and triggering ignition. Horizontal projections deflected the upward flame's trajectory and forced the flame to travel an extra horizontal distance. However, in many cases flames reverted to their original trajectory after deflection and continued spreading along the wall. At lower heat-release rates (33 to 42 kW), projections (0.1 m & 0.075 m) effectively disrupted continuous flame attachment and reduced heat transfer to the wall. The effectiveness of the projections was more pronounced at these lower intensities. At higher heat-release rates (47 to 56 kW), the effectiveness of both projections (0.1 m & 0.075 m) reduced as the intense flow exceeded the deflection capacity and allowed flames to propagate more rapidly along the wall. The length of the horizontal projection also had a significant impact on plume trajectory and ignition on the board. Longer projection, e.g., 0.2 m projection effectively prevented ignition for a 47 kW fire.

Experimental results highlighted the ability of horizontal projections in suppressing vertical flame spread along exterior combustible façades. Charring properties and vertical temperatures increased proportionally with heat-release rates but decreased with longer projections. Under similar conditions and fire sizes (33 kW & 37 kW), both projections (0.1 m & 0.075 m) delayed ignition on the board, reduced vertical flame heights and reduced vertical temperature profiles compared with scenarios without projections. However, the study also made clear the limitations of fixed-length projections, particularly during high-intensity fires. The effectiveness of horizontal projections in reducing vertical flame spread should be explored for several compartment opening dimensions, fire sizes, and projection lengths to enhance knowledge in this area.

8.2 Concluding remarks from the simulation study

The simulation study provided valuable insights into the impact of two projection types and lengths on upward flame trajectory and temperatures along the façade during a compartment fire. Both projections were effective in reducing direct flame impingement and temperatures

along the façade. The following key observations from the simulation study can be highlighted as,

- Horizontal projections significantly reduced vertical temperatures during façade fires. The projection length or depth was inversely proportional to the temperature growth along the façade.
- Open-ended projections showed a higher degree of flame deflection and temperature reduction than projections with solid wall balustrade. The reason could be that the venting flame adhered to the height of the railing before swirling upward for the solid wall balustrade projections. But due to the higher deflection degree, open-ended projections resulted in higher temperatures on the adjacent wall (1.8 m away from the fire-affected building) than the other projection type.
- Among the 0.4 m, 0.6 m, and 0.8 m open-ended projections, 0.6 m projection effectively reduced vertical temperatures in both the fire-affected building and the adjacent wall. Peak vertical temperatures remained below 130 °C at both the fire-affected wall and neighbouring wall.
- For projections with solid wall balustrades, 0.8 m projection was observed to be the most effective in reducing temperatures both for the fire-affected building and the adjacent wall. The peak vertical temperatures didn't exceed 100 °C on either of the exterior walls.

8.3 Limitations of the study

- ***External wind conditions-*** The current study didn't consider any external wind conditions or sideward wind influence. During façade fire scenarios, the trajectory of the flame can be influenced significantly by the wind direction.
- ***Extended flames beyond board-*** At higher heat-release rates, flames occasionally extended beyond the board's height and width. This study didn't consider flames that spread outside the board's dimensions.
- ***Predicted heat flux-*** No measurement system was developed to determine directly the heat flux on the board surface. The calculations were based on theoretical methods, which may deviate from the actual heat flux to the wall.

- **Char measurement precision-** Char properties were estimated based on specific visual and measured criteria which may lack precisions. Uneven char formation and potential small errors in manual measurements could affect the accuracy of the results.
- **Simulation limitations-** FDS (Fire Dynamics Simulator) relies on various assumptions and simplifications, such as uniform material properties and ideal boundary conditions, which may not fully represent the complex behaviour of real-world fire scenarios.

8.3 Further research possibilities

- **Experiments with multiple projection lengths-** Different horizontal projection lengths, both shorter and longer than those used in this study, can be useful for assessing how various projection sizes affect heat transfer and fire dynamics.
- **Variation in window dimensions-** Different compartment window sizes would provide insights like how window dimensions influence flame behaviour, heat flux distribution, and charring on façade wall. Larger or smaller openings could impact air supply, flame trajectory, affecting the fire's impact on impinging surface.
- **Extended durations-** It would be interesting to examine how extended flame exposure affects the ignition time, flame heights, temperature profiles, and charring properties at various fire sizes.
- **Façade position-** It would be interesting to investigate how a tilted façade would interact with horizontal projections on flame spreading and heat transfer.
- **Smoke accumulation-** Larger amounts of smoke may accumulate or become trapped beneath the projections. Exploring by simulation whether installing ventilation ducts on the wall corners could prevent smoke accumulation would be an interesting area of study.

Chapter 9

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APPENDIX: A

Overview of horizontal projection configurations

- Different types of projections, such as balconies, eaves, over compartment windows can be considered, along with their geometries, in the context of external fire propagation along the façade of tall buildings. The geometry of the projection above the plume venting window significantly affects the external flame behaviour and direction. The current study focused experimentally on open-ended horizontal projections over compartment openings. And in Simulation both open-ended and solid wall balustrade were considered. Various types of projections over the compartment window are categorized and illustrated below,

- Accompanying this analysis are detailed visual representations of projection types, showcasing the flame behaviour under different heat-release rates. These images illustrate the varying degrees of vertical flame spread. The visuals provide a clear comparison of how projections modify flame dynamics under increasing heat-release rate conditions and horizontal projection lengths or prolonged depths. The images here are showing only gas flames along the wall (from experimental study).

**H. Projection –
0.05 m**

33 kW

33 kW

37 kW

42 kW

47 kW

51 kW

56 kW

**H. Projection –
0.1 m**

**H. Projection –
0.075 m**

47 kW

**H. Projection –
0.2 m**

APPENDIX: B

Experimental overview and details

- Side view of the experimental process and components-

- Experimental details-

Gas flow (g/s)	HRR (kW)	Horizontal projection (m)	Exp no	Duration (s)	moisture content (%)	weight before experiment (± 5 min) gm	weight after experiment (1 ± 0.5 min) gm	weight after experiment (24 ± 1 hrs) gm
0.7	33	0.1	1	600	6.45	5796.1	5740.8	5748.6
0.7	33	0.1	2	600	6.45	5913.69	5835.8	5843.8
0.7	33	0.1	3	600	6.95	5784.5	5757.5	5772.2
0.8	37	0.1	1	600	6.45	5827.8	5753.1	5782.4
0.8	37	0.1	2	600	7.3	5868.2	5802.4	5832.7
0.8	37	0.1	3	600	6.95	5767.2	5726.7	5742.6
0.9	42	0.1	1	600	6.9	5796.89	5634.6	5678
0.9	42	0.1	2	600	6.9	5761.4	5601.2	5551.8
0.9	42	0.1	3	600	5.33	5743.6	5588.5	5606.4
1	47	0.1	1	600	6.9	5742.1	5266.7	5285.3
1	47	0.1	2	600	5.33	5770.1	5343.3	5370.3
1	47	0.1	3	600	8.69	5609.8	5202.4	5256.9
1.1	51	0.1	1	600	6.9	5809.1	5122.3	5151
1.1	51	0.1	2	600	5.33	5658.3	4952.7	5016.1
1.1	51	0.1	3	600	8.69	5691.2	4960.6	5004.2
1.2	56	0.1	1	600	6.93	5723.8	4964.8	5015.6
1.2	56	0.1	2	600	8.02	5643.8	4993.2	5092.59
1.2	56	0.1	3	600	8.69	5664.2	4819.29	4880.2
0.7	33	0.075	1	600	7.05	5665.5	5642.8	5646.8
0.7	33	0.075	2	600	8.45	5497.1	5496.9	5509.3
0.8	37	0.075	1	600	7.96	5677	5637.5	5681.4
0.8	37	0.075	2	600	8.45	5574.9	5472.1	5589.3
0.8	37	0.075	3	600	8.45	5687.6	5576.2	5488.2
0.9	42	0.075	1	600	7.4	5620.2	5274.3	5298.3
0.9	42	0.075	2	600	8.45	5587.2	5285.3	5340.2
1	47	0.075	1	600	7.4	5815.5	5310.2	5330.1
1	47	0.075	2	600	7.96	5715.5	5131.8	5179.1
1.1	51	0.075	1	600	7.4	5784.1	5155.2	5198
1.1	51	0.075	2	600	8.02	5702.3	5054.7	5092.69
1.2	56	0.075	1	600	7.96	5732.1	4854.4	4931.6
1.2	56	0.075	2	600	8.02	5752.5	4943.4	4990.5

APPENDIX: C

Supplementary temperature data

- Gas temperatures along the board height and temperatures 0.006 m (6 mm) inside the board have been plotted against time (min). Thermocouple data at every 0.1 m height up to 0.9 m vertical height (board height) for all heat-release rates and horizontal projections have been represented.

0.1 m horizontal projection

0.075 m horizontal projection

- **Additional experimental data-**

HRR- 60 kW

Horizontal projection- 0.1 m

Number of experiments- 1

Experimental duration- 10 min (600 seconds)

Ignition on board surface- at 113 seconds

0.2 m horizontal projection

HRR- 47 kW

Horizontal projection- 0.2 m

Number of experiments- 1

Experimental duration- 10 min (600 seconds)

Ignition on board surface- No ignition

0.05 m horizontal projection

HRR- 33 kW

Horizontal projection- 0.05 m

Number of experiments- 3

Experimental duration- 10 min (600 seconds)

Ignition on board surface- No ignition

Non dimensional correlation between vertical temperature and heat-release rate-

Non-dimensional temperature difference, $\Theta = \frac{\Delta T}{T_{\infty}} \approx \text{function} \left(\frac{H_t}{H} \right)$

Here,

H = Characteristic vertical height,

H_t = Thermocouple position height,

ΔT = Temperature difference at certain height

Temperature difference normalized with non-dimensional heat-release rate and vertical height normalized with thermocouple position heights.

APPENDIX: D

Charring properties

- Char depths measurement (0.1 m H. projection) - Averaged data with standard deviation

Height (cm)	42 kW	42 kW	42 kW	47 kW	47 kW	47 kW	51 kW	51 kW	51 kW	56 kW	56 kW	56 kW
120	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
115	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
110	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
105	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
100	0	0	0	0.0296	0.06	0.0904	0.04907	0.07667	0.10427		0	
95	0	0	0	0.0182	0.07	0.1218	0.0584	0.102	0.1456	0.03305	0.07	0.10695
90	0	0	0	0.07784	0.10714	0.13644	0.10605	0.11875	0.13145	0.02872	0.09	0.15128
85	0	0	0	0.1231	0.14	0.1569	0.13205	0.15625	0.18045	0.03735	0.1175	0.19765
80	0	0	0	0.1001	0.1425	0.1849	0.1152	0.159	0.2028	0.09929	0.152	0.20471
75	0.032	0.045	0.058	0.11567	0.15667	0.19767	0.13723	0.17833	0.21943	0.12824	0.19364	0.25903
70	0.0565	0.0725	0.0885	0.14446	0.19556	0.24666	0.15224	0.21154	0.27084	0.14499	0.19067	0.23634
65	0.0937	0.118	0.1423	0.14792	0.21182	0.27572	0.19651	0.23071	0.26491	0.17586	0.24375	0.31164
60	0.1336	0.145	0.1564	0.1782	0.2225	0.2668	0.2027	0.25	0.2973	0.20973	0.26056	0.31138
55	0.15017	0.16857	0.18697	0.21037	0.26667	0.32297	0.22672	0.27882	0.33092	0.25306	0.30947	0.36589
50	0.17385	0.19375	0.21365	0.24966	0.27846	0.30726	0.29047	0.32647	0.36247	0.27415	0.3365	0.39885
45	0.18241	0.22111	0.25981	0.2696	0.3	0.3304	0.28758	0.33278	0.37798	0.27215	0.35476	0.43738
40	0.1969	0.24	0.2831	0.28534	0.33714	0.38894	0.30848	0.35368	0.39888	0.32478	0.38048	0.43617
35	0.2344	0.262	0.2896	0.35421	0.38071	0.40721	0.35855	0.37895	0.39935	0.33394	0.41238	0.49082
30	0.2804	0.324	0.3676	0.37906	0.41286	0.44666	0.34913	0.41053	0.47193	0.41083	0.45	0.48917
25	0.32639	0.33909	0.35179	0.4449	0.48	0.5151	0.38414	0.43684	0.48954	0.41945	0.48048	0.5415
20	0.35853	0.38273	0.40693	0.46464	0.49714	0.52964	0.41476	0.47556	0.53636	0.46329	0.5105	0.55772
15	0.38893	0.43273	0.47653	0.42542	0.46462	0.50382	0.44848	0.47778	0.50708	0.45005	0.52789	0.60574
10	0.33526	0.37636	0.41746	0.35717	0.41167	0.46617	0.4931	0.51	0.5269	0.47282	0.51895	0.56508
5	0.33848	0.39778	0.45708	0.24213	0.26333	0.28453	0.38385	0.42625	0.46865	0.56456	0.65	0.73544
CM	0.21877	0.24791	0.27705	0.23088	0.26994	0.309	0.25474	0.29455	0.33436	0.26823	0.32892	0.38962
	0.11484	0.12393	0.13402	0.13861	0.13758	0.13772	0.13514	0.13699	0.1403	0.1655	0.16826	0.17226
MM	2.18768	2.47908	2.77048	2.30879	2.69939	3.08999	2.54735	2.94545	3.34355	2.68227	3.28922	3.89618
	1.14843	1.23928	1.34016	1.38614	1.37582	1.3772	1.35137	1.36989	1.40304	1.65502	1.68257	1.72265

- Char depths measurement (0.075 m H. projection) - Averaged data with standard deviation

Height (cm)	37 kW	37 kW	37 kW	42 kW	42 kW	42 kW	47 kW	47 kW	47 kW	51 kW	51 kW	51 kW	56 kW	56 kW	56 kW
120	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		0
115	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		0
110	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		0
105	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0666 ₇	0.0577 ₇	0.0755 ₇
100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0466 ₇	0.0356 ₇	0.0576 ₇	0.0625	0.0421	0.0829	0.112	0.0748 ₇	0.1491 ₃
95	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.076	0.0633	0.0887	0.1083 ₃	0.0795 ₃	0.1371 ₃	0.1516 ₇	0.0770 ₈	0.2262 ₅
90	0	0	0	0.0466 ₇	0.0173 ₇	0.0759 ₇	0.1	0.0658	0.1342	0.1525	0.1221	0.1829	0.17	0.1232 ₈	0.2167 ₂
85	0	0	0	0.102	0.0778	0.1262	0.1387 ₅	0.0914 ₅	0.1860 ₅	0.2055 ₆	0.1537 ₆	0.2573 ₆	0.1975	0.1412 ₈	0.2537 ₂
80	0	0	0	0.1416 ₇	0.0978 ₇	0.1854 ₇	0.1655 ₆	0.1134 ₆	0.2176 ₆	0.2263 ₆	0.1998 ₆	0.2528 ₆	0.204	0.1397 ₁	0.2682 ₉
75	0	0	0	0.175	0.1339	0.2161	0.1977 ₈	0.1617 ₈	0.2337 ₈	0.2533 ₃	0.2195 ₃	0.2871 ₃	0.2518 ₂	0.1924 ₄	0.3112
70	0	0	0	0.1771 ₄	0.1250 ₄	0.2292 ₄	0.1945 ₅	0.1493 ₅	0.2397 ₅	0.2707 ₇	0.2296 ₇	0.3118 ₇	0.2585 ₇	0.2153 ₆	0.3017 ₉
65	0	0	0	0.1937 ₅	0.1577 ₅	0.2297 ₅	0.2091 ₇	0.1639 ₇	0.2543 ₇	0.2907 ₁	0.2314 ₁	0.3500 ₁	0.2893 ₃	0.2107 ₄	0.3679 ₃
60	0	0	0	0.2011 ₁	0.1559 ₁	0.2463 ₁	0.2376 ₉	0.2172 ₉	0.2580 ₉	0.2893 ₈	0.2551 ₈	0.3235 ₈	0.3141 ₂	0.2724 ₅	0.3557 ₉
55	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.212	0.1668	0.2572	0.2707 ₇	0.2093 ₇	0.3321 ₇	0.3493 ₈	0.3020 ₈	0.3966 ₈	0.323	0.2569	0.3891
50	0.0525	0.0249	0.0801	0.242	0.2216	0.2624	0.2593 ₈	0.2066 ₈	0.3120 ₈	0.3505 ₃	0.2984 ₃	0.4026 ₃	0.3755	0.3064 ₈	0.4445 ₂
45	0.094	0.0457 ₁	0.1422 ₉	0.2416 ₇	0.2005 ₇	0.2827 ₇	0.305	0.2442	0.3658	0.361	0.325	0.397	0.408	0.3333 ₈	0.4826 ₂
40	0.1316 ₇	0.0553 ₅	0.2079 ₈	0.2584 ₆	0.1991 ₆	0.3177 ₆	0.3183 ₃	0.2890 ₃	0.3476 ₃	0.397	0.3518	0.4422	0.449	0.3982 ₁	0.4997 ₉
35	0.1542 ₉	0.0893 ₆	0.2192 ₁	0.29	0.2558	0.3242	0.3633 ₃	0.3464 ₃	0.3802 ₃	0.429	0.3838	0.4742	0.4652 ₄	0.3796 ₃	0.5508 ₅
30	0.1928 ₆	0.1375 ₂	0.2482	0.3061 ₅	0.2588 ₅	0.3534 ₅	0.3844 ₄	0.3420 ₄	0.4268 ₄	0.4325	0.4121	0.4529	0.4813 ₆	0.4486 ₅	0.5140 ₈
25	0.22	0.1494 ₈	0.2905 ₂	0.3384 ₆	0.2863 ₆	0.3905 ₆	0.4282 ₄	0.3872 ₄	0.4692 ₄	0.4465	0.3851	0.5079	0.5272 ₇	0.4800 ₉	0.5744 ₆
20	0.2512 ₅	0.2236 ₅	0.2788 ₅	0.36	0.324	0.396	0.4543 ₈	0.4032 ₈	0.5054 ₈	0.4789 ₅	0.4262 ₅	0.5316 ₅	0.5631 ₈	0.5262 ₃	0.6001 ₃
15	0.2825	0.2389	0.3261	0.3869 ₂	0.3417 ₂	0.4321 ₂	0.4546 ₇	0.3907 ₇	0.5185 ₇	0.4744 ₄	0.4136 ₄	0.5352 ₄	0.5995 ₂	0.5382 ₄	0.6608 ₁
10	0.2066 ₇	0.1939 ₇	0.2193 ₇	0.4081 ₈	0.3629 ₈	0.4533 ₈	0.4838 ₅	0.4395 ₅	0.5281 ₅	0.5075	0.4782	0.5368	0.5904 ₈	0.5103 ₂	0.6706 ₃
5	0	0	0	0.3388 ₉	0.2774 ₉	0.4002 ₉	0.6258 ₃	0.5695 ₃	0.6821 ₃	0.5953 ₈	0.5784 ₈	0.6122 ₈	0.5255	0.4727 ₉	0.5782 ₁
CM	0.1477 ₉	0.1098 ₉	0.1866	0.2455 ₆	0.2033 ₉	0.2877 ₃	0.2857 ₂	0.2445 ₁	0.3269 ₃	0.3340 ₈	0.2944	0.3737 ₆	0.3487 ₅	0.2931 ₄	0.4043 ₆
	0.0923 ₆	0.0833	0.1071 ₃	0.0997 ₄	0.0957 ₅	0.1047 ₂	0.1532 ₅	0.1464 ₂	0.1614 ₁	0.1406 ₃	0.1384 ₁	0.1441 ₉	0.1656 ₈	0.1617 ₄	0.1716 ₁
MM	1.4779 ₃	1.0989 ₄	1.8660 ₂	2.4556	2.0338 ₇	2.8773 ₂	2.8571 ₈	2.4450 ₈	3.2692 ₈	3.3408 ₁	2.9440 ₁	3.7376 ₁	3.4874 ₉	2.9313 ₇	4.0436 ₁
	0.9235 ₇	0.8329 ₈	1.0713 ₃	0.9973 ₉	0.9575 ₂	1.0472	1.5325	1.4641 ₇	1.6140 ₇	1.4063 ₅	1.3841 ₁	1.4418 ₈	1.6568 ₂	1.6174	1.7161

- Dominating wind flow direction burned and charred to the side edge of the board.

- Deformation at lower end of board panels. Degree of deformation increased with fire size,

Angle of deformation $\sim (3 - 7)^\circ$. Reference picture from one of the experimental studies at 51 kW HRR.

- Contour plots to distinguish the charring regions on board surface (reference picture- 47 kW HRR at 0.1 and 0.075 m projections, exposure duration- 10 min (600 s)),

0.1 m H. Projection
47 kW HRR

0.075 m H. Projection
47 kW HRR

- Char depths with averaged temperatures (°C) across heat-release rates,

APPENDIX: E

Heat flux calculation examples

- Heat flux calculations as function of time
- Reference heat flux- 56 kW (0.1 m horizontal projection) at 0.5 m wall height

Time (s)	Temp-50 cm out	Temp-50 cm in	co efficient	convective heat flux	Emmissivity-wall	STEFan	T*4	Flame height, z	constant	vent height, h	h_w	z-h_w/z	sum	h_l	flame thickness	constant	equal	emissivityflame	Radiative heat flux	IF value (Radiative)	Total heat flux
1	143.21	19.8335	0.0009	0.11144	0.82	5.7E-11	4.2E+08	0.51465	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.02846	0.00759	0.1	0.10759	0.3	0.96824	0.03176	0.00062	0.00062	0.11206
3	193.021	20.4973	0.0009	0.15583	0.82	5.7E-11	1.4E+09	0.55595	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.10064	0.02684	0.1	0.12684	0.3	0.96266	0.03734	0.00241	0.00241	0.15824
6	242.082	21.2241	0.0009	0.19948	0.82	5.7E-11	3.4E+09	0.57727	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.13386	0.0357	0.1	0.1357	0.3	0.96011	0.03989	0.00637	0.00637	0.20585
8	265.983	21.497	0.0009	0.22083	0.82	5.7E-11	5E+09	0.57745	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.13413	0.03577	0.1	0.13577	0.3	0.96009	0.03991	0.00929	0.00929	0.23011
11	281.041	21.7863	0.0009	0.23417	0.82	5.7E-11	6.2E+09	0.58932	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.15156	0.04042	0.1	0.14042	0.3	0.95875	0.04125	0.01196	0.01196	0.24613
13	288.511	22.0943	0.0009	0.24083	0.82	5.7E-11	6.9E+09	0.57475	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.13006	0.03468	0.1	0.13468	0.3	0.9604	0.0396	0.01276	0.01276	0.25339
16	290.274	22.4256	0.0009	0.24193	0.82	5.7E-11	7.1E+09	0.55859	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.10489	0.02797	0.1	0.12797	0.3	0.96234	0.03766	0.01243	0.01243	0.25436
18	289.63	22.7863	0.0009	0.24102	0.82	5.7E-11	7E+09	0.54417	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.08116	0.02164	0.1	0.12164	0.3	0.96416	0.03584	0.01172	0.01172	0.25274
21	284.676	23.1747	0.0009	0.2362	0.82	5.7E-11	6.6E+09	0.55817	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.10421	0.02779	0.1	0.12779	0.3	0.96239	0.03761	0.01148	0.01148	0.24768
23	284.897	23.5933	0.0009	0.23602	0.82	5.7E-11	6.6E+09	0.5511	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.09272	0.02473	0.1	0.12473	0.3	0.96327	0.03673	0.01125	0.01125	0.24727
26	288.503	24.0358	0.0009	0.23887	0.82	5.7E-11	6.9E+09	0.569	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.12127	0.03234	0.1	0.13234	0.3	0.96108	0.03892	0.01254	0.01254	0.25141
28	299.776	24.5089	0.0009	0.24863	0.82	5.7E-11	8.1E+09	0.5566	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.10169	0.02712	0.1	0.12712	0.3	0.96258	0.03742	0.01405	0.01405	0.26268
31	314.441	25.0108	0.0009	0.26142	0.82	5.7E-11	9.8E+09	0.55893	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.10544	0.02812	0.1	0.12812	0.3	0.96229	0.03771	0.01714	0.01714	0.27856
33	332.376	25.5449	0.0009	0.27714	0.82	5.7E-11	1.2E+10	0.55167	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.09366	0.02497	0.1	0.12497	0.3	0.9632	0.0368	0.02088	0.02088	0.29802
36	346.132	26.1239	0.0009	0.28904	0.82	5.7E-11	1.4E+10	0.53027	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.05708	0.01522	0.1	0.11522	0.3	0.96602	0.03398	0.02267	0.02267	0.31171
38	362.284	26.7693	0.0009	0.30305	0.82	5.7E-11	1.7E+10	0.51313	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.02559	0.00683	0.1	0.10683	0.3	0.96846	0.03154	0.02526	0.02526	0.32831
41	372.309	27.4895	0.0009	0.31145	0.82	5.7E-11	1.9E+10	0.53213	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.06039	0.0161	0.1	0.1161	0.3	0.96577	0.03423	0.03058	0.03058	0.34203
43	379.832	28.293	0.0009	0.31752	0.82	5.7E-11	2.1E+10	0.53747	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.06971	0.01859	0.1	0.11859	0.3	0.96505	0.03495	0.03382	0.03382	0.35134
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
582	291.499	139.62	0.0009	0.13718	0.82	5.7E-11	7.2E+09	0.5893	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.15149	0.0404	0.1	0.1404	0.3	0.95876	0.04124	0.01385	0.01385	0.15103
585	294.506	139.701	0.0009	0.13982	0.82	5.7E-11	7.5E+09	0.5988	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.165	0.044	0.1	0.144	0.3	0.95772	0.04228	0.01479	0.01479	0.15461
588	295.06	139.782	0.0009	0.14025	0.82	5.7E-11	7.6E+09	0.6047	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.1731	0.04616	0.1	0.14616	0.3	0.9571	0.0429	0.01512	0.01512	0.15537
591	294.824	139.862	0.0009	0.13997	0.82	5.7E-11	7.6E+09	0.5872	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.1485	0.0396	0.1	0.1396	0.3	0.95898	0.04102	0.01441	0.01441	0.15437
594	294.599	139.942	0.0009	0.13969	0.82	5.7E-11	7.5E+09	0.6252	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.20026	0.0534	0.1	0.1534	0.3	0.95502	0.04498	0.01575	0.01575	0.15544
597	289.209	140.021	0.0009	0.13475	0.82	5.7E-11	7E+09	0.6252	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.20026	0.0534	0.1	0.1534	0.3	0.95502	0.04498	0.01463	0.01463	0.14938
600	277.406	140.095	0.0009	0.12402	0.82	5.7E-11	5.9E+09	0.6170	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.18967	0.05058	0.1	0.15058	0.3	0.95583	0.04417	0.01216	0.01216	0.13618
603	262.51	140.172	0.0009	0.1105	0.82	5.7E-11	4.7E+09	0.5790	0.66667	0.4	0.5	0.13839	0.03637	0.1	0.13637	0.3	0.95991	0.04009	0.00885	0.00885	0.11935

- Averaged heat flux calculations (radiative + convective) based on M. Law and Oleszkiewicz's method [11][18][22],
- Reference heat flux- 47 kW (0.1 m horizontal projection) at 0.5 m wall height

0.1 m H. Projection																
	h	z	h_w	z-h/h	h_l	sum	λ	exp	ε flame	T	T ⁴	σ	ε wall	q _{rad}	F value	
0.66667	0.4	0.641	0.1	0.84239376	0.1	0.225065003	0.325065	0.3	0.9070847	0.092915	659.70496	1.894E+11	5.67E-11	0.82	0.818245	0.81824439
0.66667	0.4	0.641	0.2	0.68798752	0.1	0.183463339	0.28346334	0.3	0.9184765	0.081524	706.14564	2.486E+11	5.67E-11	0.82	0.9424473	0.94244728
0.66667	0.4	0.641	0.3	0.531981273	0.1	0.141861674	0.24186167	0.3	0.9300113	0.069989	704.81373	2.468E+11	5.67E-11	0.82	0.803002	0.803002
0.66667	0.4	0.641	0.4	0.375975039	0.1	0.10026001	0.20026001	0.3	0.9416911	0.058309	672.1163	2.04E+11	5.67E-11	0.82	0.5523295	0.55232951
0.66667	0.4	0.641	0.5	0.219989799	0.1	0.058959346	0.15895935	0.3	0.9535175	0.048493	657.44279	1.863E+11	5.67E-11	0.82	0.4037553	0.40375535
0.66667	0.4	0.641	0.6	0.063962559	0.1	0.017056682	0.11705668	0.3	0.9654324	0.034506	620.66134	1.484E+11	5.67E-11	0.82	0.2388838	0.23888384
0.66667	0.4	0.641	0.7	-0.092043682	0.1	-0.024544498	0.07454502	0.3	0.9776178	0.022382	596.27849	1.264E+11	5.67E-11	0.82	0.1319518	0.13195176
0.66667	0.4	0.641	0.8	-0.248049922	0.1	-0.06614665	0.03385335	0.3	0.9898954	0.010105	563.33574	1.007E+11	5.67E-11	0.82	0.0473136	0.04731356
0.66667	0.4	0.641	0.9	-0.404056162	0.1	-0.10774831	-0.00774831	0.3	1.0023272	-0.00233	521.6135	7.403E+10	5.67E-11	0.82	-0.00801	0

IFRR (kW)	Horizontal extension (m)	Height above the vent along (m)	Avg. fire plume temperature (K)	Wall emissivity, ε_w	Radiant heat flux density (kW/m ²)
42	0.1	0.1	853.7049561	0.82	0.818244398
42	0.1	0.2	706.1456415	0.82	0.942447276
42	0.1	0.3	704.8137317	0.82	0.803011989
42	0.1	0.4	672.1163024	0.82	0.552329513
42	0.1	0.5	657.4427902	0.82	0.403755347
42	0.1	0.6	620.6613415	0.82	0.238883838
42	0.1	0.7	596.2784854	0.82	0.131951762
42	0.1	0.8	563.3357415	0.82	0.047313559
42	0.1	0.9	521.6135024	0.82	0
42	0.75	0.1	734.66	0.82	1.126536536
42	0.75	0.2	749.84	0.82	1.060932929
42	0.75	0.3	714.97	0.82	0.753045534
42	0.75	0.4	694.61	0.82	0.554163408
42	0.75	0.5	673.24	0.82	0.384570444
42	0.75	0.6	631.01	0.82	0.21571022
42	0.75	0.7	593.02	0.82	0.104108458
42	0.75	0.8	561.41	0.82	0.03149611
42	0.75	0.9	500.09	0.82	0

$$q''_{rad} = \epsilon_f \times \epsilon_w \times \sigma \times (T^4)$$

$$\epsilon = 1 - (e^{-0.3 \times \lambda})$$

$$\lambda = \frac{2}{3} \times h \times \left(\frac{T - h_w}{z} \right) + h_l$$

σ Stefan boltzman constant (kW/m²·K⁻⁴) 5.67E-11
 z Peak flame height (m) Variable
 h Height of the opening (m) 0.4
 h_w Vertical height from the opening (m) variable

A_w	Area of the compartment	0.8
d	Depth of the compartment	0.4
l_w	Length of the compartment	0.015
Q	IFRR (kW)	33
(ΔH) _u	Heat of combustion of total area of room boundaries	46.45
A_L	Room boundaries	0.56
h	Vent height (m)	0.4
W	Width of the compartment	0.2

$$q'' = \alpha (T_f - T_w)$$

$$\alpha = 0.0132 \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{A_w} \right)^{0.6} \times \left(\frac{1}{d} \right)^{0.4} \quad \alpha = k \left(\frac{R}{A_w} \right)^{0.6}$$

$$R = 0.18 (1 - \exp(-0.036 \times A_L / (A_w h^{1/2}))) / (d/W)^{1/2}$$

R_Thomas										R_Beckhaus		
A_L	A_w	h	h ^{0.5}	d	w	dW ^{0.5}	R_Thomas	constat	Q	H _c	R_Beckhaus	
0.18	-0.036	0.56	0.8	0.4	0.015	0.1242636	0.007031	0.0049171	0.0015	33	46.3	0.00107

Law										Oleszkiewicz		
Const.	R_Thomas	R_Beckhaus	A_w	d	R_Thomas/A_w	R_Beckhaus/A_w	l/d	α_Thomas	α_Beckhaus	Const.	R_Thomas	α_Beckhaus
0.015	0.004917	0.00107	0.8	0.4	0.0062146	0.001322018	2.5	0.0009032	0.000359	0.015	0.00062	0.000245

IFRR (kW)	Horizontal extension (m)	Height above the vent along the wall (m)	Avg. fire plume temperature (K)	Avg. Wall temperature (0.6 cm inside) (K)	Bearing rate, m (kg/s) - Thomas eq.	Bearing rate, m (kg/s) - Beckhaus	Heat transfer coefficient, α (kW/m ² ·K)				Convective heat flux density, Q _{conv.} (kW/m ²)				Radiative heat flux density to the wall (kW/m ²)		Total heat flux density (kW/m ²) by Law		Total heat flux density (kW/m ²) by Oleszkiewicz	
							R_Thomas		R_Beckhaus		R_Thomas		R_Beckhaus		R_Thomas	R_Beckhaus	R_Thomas	R_Beckhaus	R_Thomas	R_Beckhaus
							Law	Oleszkiewicz	Law	Oleszkiewicz	Law	Oleszkiewicz	Law	Oleszkiewicz	Law	Oleszkiewicz	Law	Oleszkiewicz	Law	Oleszkiewicz
42	0.1	0.1	853.7049561	342.065834	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000414284	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.2863	0.131596042	0.11386798	0.07773114	0.818244398	1.1051452	0.32121391	0.34394103	0.83576128	
42	0.1	0.2	706.1456415	345.645015	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.325614	0.222277332	0.128233068	0.088220004	0.942447276	1.26610612	1.07168034	1.16472521	1.03061723	
42	0.1	0.3	704.8137317	340.102215	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.328417	0.224874288	0.130742597	0.089250473	0.803011989	1.1324283	0.933746	1.02786629	0.93226241	
42	0.1	0.4	672.1163024	340.329771	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.296973	0.20457359	0.118939515	0.081193227	0.552329513	0.851916	0.6721459	0.75780837	0.54428239	
42	0.1	0.5	657.4427902	328.419615	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.231163	0.202863526	0.117348361	0.080516391	0.403755347	0.7100338	0.52170431	0.60662487	0.484272338	
42	0.1	0.6	620.6613415	317.427324	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.173869	0.166368414	0.108704006	0.074205591	0.238883838	0.519193	0.34876784	0.42502825	0.312289828	
42	0.1	0.7	596.2784854	321.485376	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.1442	0.163431667	0.089508088	0.067245822	0.131951762	0.3797514	0.23009385	0.30088343	0.198719754	
42	0.1	0.8	563.3357415	314.260514	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.224972	0.15375341	0.083289172	0.060932597	0.047313559	0.2122854	0.13660273	0.2008889	0.10826615	
42	0.1	0.9	521.6135024	313.557322	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.187922	0.128283543	0.074584443	0.050914522	0	0.187922	0.07458444	0.12828354	0.050914522	
42	0.75	0.1	734.657341	368.301122	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.330901	0.22588739	0.131331618	0.088652563	1.126536536	1.4574378	1.25788815	1.35242393	1.216185099	
42	0.75	0.2	749.8408634	370.586178	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.341469	0.233104136	0.135252886	0.09251575	1.060832929	1.4023621	1.19641881	1.29339436	1.153408678	
42	0.75	0.3	714.9748244	353.645493	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.320933	0.219086574	0.127377603	0.086353384	0.753045534	1.073844	0.88042314	0.9732121	0.833989318	
42	0.75	0.4	694.6130584	354.85428	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.306973	0.203493914	0.121797494	0.083144164	0.554163408	0.8640427	0.6759609	0.76595232	0.637107172	
42	0.75	0.5	673.278561	345.389061	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.286122	0.20245486	0.117528003	0.080229627	0.384570444	0.8809324	0.50232845	0.58701593	0.465100071	
42	0.75	0.6	631.0162585	326.630315	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.214526	0.187616451	0.103156661	0.074497004	0.21571022	0.4906374	0.324826668	0.40338747	0.230198025	
42	0.75	0.7	593.0202683	336.637841	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.235712	0.150806001	0.091908544	0.062740682	0.104108458	0.33566	0.186017	0.26218006	0.16648315	
42	0.75	0.8	561.4058049	323.744189	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.203243	0.142838213	0.083046573	0.056611522	0.03149611	0.2407391	0.11454268	0.17433432	0.088987842	
42	0.75	0.9	500.0344268	323.317149	0.004917	0.001066	0.000903	0.000616581	0.000358482	0.000244715	0.193828	0.109627609	0.061954423	0.043112669	0	0.1518281	0.06195442	0.10962761	0.043112669	

- Averaged calculative heat flux densities along the board height based on Law & Oleszkiewicz's heat transfer coefficient equation-

APPENDIX: F

FDS input details and additional data

- Simulation details -

Projection length (m)	Projection type	simulation time (s)	Thermocouples
0.0	N/A	600.0	8 + 6
0.4	open-ended	600.0	8 + 6
0.6	open-ended	600.0	8 + 6
0.8	open-ended	600.0	8 + 6
0.4	balustrade	600.0	8 + 6
0.6	balustrade	600.0	8 + 6
0.8	balustrade	600.0	8 + 6

- Mesh –

&MESH ID='Mesh01-02', IJK=50,30,30, XB=0.0,5.0,0.0,3.0,2.5,5.0/

&MESH ID='Mesh03', IJK=50,30,30, XB=0.0,5.0,0.0,3.0,2.5,5.0/

- Reaction –

&REAC ID='POLYURETHANE_GM27',

FYI='SFPE Handbook, GM27',

FUEL='REAC_FUEL', C=1.0, H=1.7, O=0.3, N=0.08,

CO_YIELD=0.042, SOOT_YIELD=0.198/

- Burner –

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&SURF ID='Fire burner',
COLOR='RED',
HRRPUA=3100.0,
RAMP_Q='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', TMP_FRONT=500.0/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=0.0, F=0.0/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=10.0, F=0.0/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=53.0, F=0.027974/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=96.0, F=0.111894/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=139.0, F=0.251762/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=182.0, F=0.447577/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=225.0, F=0.69934/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=268.0, F=1.0/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=297.0, F=1.0/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=340.0, F=0.69934/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=383.0, F=0.447577/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=426.0, F=0.251762/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=469.0, F=0.111894/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=512.0, F=0.027974/
&RAMP ID='Fire burner_RAMP_Q', T=555.0, F=0.0/

```

- Calculated HRR curve -

- Temperature contours for different horizontal projection lengths and types -

Raw slice (soot and flame)

Temperature slice
contour- 0 m H.
Proj.

Temperature slice
contour- 0.4 m H.
Proj.
(open-ended)

Temperature slice
contour- 0.6 m H.
Proj.
(open-ended)

Temperature slice
contour- 0.8 m H.
Proj.
(open-ended)

Temperature slice
contour- 0.4 m H.
Proj.
(solid wall
balustrade)

Temperature slice
contour- 0.6 m H.
Proj.
(solid wall
balustrade)

Temperature slice
contour- 0.8 m H.
Proj.
(solid wall
balustrade)

- Impact of Coandă effect on solid wall balustrade projection –

- Open ended projections :

- Projections with solid wall balustrade:

**Due to
Coandă effect**

When a flame flows near a surface, it naturally ‘sticks’ to it due to differences in air pressure on either side of the flame. With solid wall balustrades, the vertical railing height (0.4 m) stabilized the flame’s path, leading to a lower deflection.

- Time vs temperature development plots for different horizontal projection lengths and types -

Thermocouple positions

H. Projection – 0 m (vertical temperature data along the affected building façade and at 1.8 m distance)

H. Projection – 0.4 m (open-ended)

H. Projection – 0.6 m (open ended)

H. Projection – 0.8m (open ended)

H. Projection – 0.4m (balustrade)

H. Projection – 0.6 m (balustrade)

H. Projection – 0.8 m (balustrade)